

**ASSESSMENT OF FARMERS' COMPLIANCE WITH FOOT AND MOUTH
DISEASE CONTROL PRACTICES AMONG DAIRY CATTLE FARMS
IN BYERIMA SUB-COUNTY, KYANKWANZI DISTRICT**

**BY
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AND TECHNOLOGY**

MAY, 2025

DECLARATION

I hereby declare to the best of my knowledge that this research dissertation is a product of my own work and has never been submitted to any university or higher institution of learning for any academic award.

Signature

Date

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APPROVAL

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to my beloved father, Bakubye Stephen, whose unwavering support in physically facilitating my movements across various dairy farms in Kyankwanzi District was instrumental in the success of this study.

I also dedicate this work to my dearest mother, Nankwanga Catherine, whose boundless financial support, enduring love, and constant words of encouragement gave me the strength to keep moving forward, even when the road seemed tough.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

APPROVAL	ii
DEDICATION	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iv
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS.....	x
ABSTRACT.....	xi
CHAPTER ONE	1
1.0 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background of the study	1
1.2 Problem statement.....	3
1.3 Objectives of the study.....	4
1.3.1 General objective	4
1.3.2 Specific objectives	4
1.4 Research questions.....	4
1.5 Scope of the study.....	4
1.5.1 Geographical scope of the study	4
1.5.2 Content scope of the study	5
1.5.3 Time scope of the study	5
1.6 Significance of the study.....	5
1.7 Justification of the study	6
1.8 Conceptual framework for the study.....	6
CHAPTER TWO	8
LITERATURE REVIEW	8
2 .0 Introduction.....	8
2.1 Dairy production	8
2.1.1 Current status of dairy production	8
2.1.2 Global milk production	8
2.1.3 Milk production in Africa	8
2.1.4 Milk production in Uganda.....	9
2.1.5 Trends and drivers of dairy production.....	9
2.2 Classification of dairy production systems globally	10
2.2.1 Traditional classification of dairy systems.....	10
2.2.2 Modern classification of dairy production systems	10
2.2.3 Characteristics of intensive vs. extensive dairy systems.....	11
2.2.4 Milk production systems used in Uganda	11
2.3 Challenges faced by the dairy sector.....	11

2.3.1 Limited infrastructures	11
2.3.2 Genetic limitations of indigenous cattle in Ethiopia	12
2.3.3 Disease-related mortality and acaricide resistance	12
2.4 Foot and Mouth Disease as an economically important disease on dairy cattle farms	12
2.4.1 Etiology of Foot and Mouth Disease	12
2.4.2 Epidemiology of Foot and Mouth Disease	13
2.4.3 Signs and symptoms of dairy cattle suffering from foot and mouth disease	13
2.4.4 Risk factors that could predispose dairy cattle to foot and mouth disease.....	14
2.4.5 Treatment of foot and mouth disease among dairy cattle famers	14
2.5 Level of knowledge and awareness among dairy cattle farmers regarding FMD and its control practices	15
2.6 Factors influencing the compliance of dairy cattle farmers with control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease	16
2.6.1 Poor communication	16
2.6.2 Source of information	16
2.6.3 High cost of vaccines	17
2.7 Challenges hindering dairy cattle farmers from complying with the control practices of Foot and Mouth.....	17
2.7.1 Socio-Cultural and knowledge-based constraints	17
2.7.2 Financial and Economic Barriers.....	17
2.7.3 Limited knowledge and awareness of the vaccine	18
2.7.4 Poor communication	18
2.7.5 Institutional and Organizational Constraints.....	18
2.7.6 Limited compensation of the lost animals	18
2.7.7 Unavailability of veterinary service providers.....	18
CHAPTER THREE	20
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	20
3 .0 Introduction	20
3.1 Study area description.....	20
3.1.1 Map of Uganda showing the study location of Byerima sub county, Kyankwanzi district, central Uganda.	21
3.2 Research design	21
3.3 Study population	21
3.4 Sampling	22
3.4.1 Sample size determination	22
3.4.2 Sampling techniques and procedure	23
3.5 Data collection	23

3.5.1 Methods of data collection.....	23
3.5.2 Tools of data collection.....	24
3.6 Data Analysis.....	24
3.7 Ethical Considerations.....	24
3.8 Limitations and Delimitation.....	24
3.8.1 Limitations.....	25
3.8.2 Delimitations.....	25
CHAPTER FOUR.....	26
PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION, AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS.....	26
4.0 Introduction.....	26
4.1 Socio-demographic characteristics.....	26
4.2 Knowledge and awareness of FMD and its control practices among dairy cattle farmers.....	31
4.2.1 Familiarity with Foot and Mouth Disease.....	31
4.2.2 Knowledge of respondents on the signs and symptoms of Foot and mouth disease in cattle.....	32
4.3 Awareness of the FMD control practices recommended by veterinary authorities.....	34
4.4 Treatment of Sick Cattle in 2023 and 2024.....	35
4.5 Quarantine measures for new cattle introduced on the farm.....	36
4.6 Vaccination against Foot and Mouth Disease FMD.....	38
4.7 Reasons for not vaccinating their cattle.....	39
4.8 Cleaning and disinfection practices of barns and farm equipment.....	41
4.9 Challenges to maintaining regular cleaning and disinfection practices.....	42
4.10 Challenges to accessing veterinary services.....	43
4.11 Challenges to compliance with FMD control practices.....	45
CHAPTER FIVE.....	47
CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	47
5.0 Introduction.....	47
5.1 Conclusions.....	47
5.2 Recommendations.....	48
5.2.1 Recommendations to Governments, Animal Health Organizations, and Veterinary Associations.....	48
5.2.2 Recommendations to Researchers, Extension Agents, and Agricultural Organizations.....	48
5.2.3 Recommendations to farmers.....	49
REFERENCES.....	50
APPENDICES.....	63

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1:showing the relationship between the level of knowledge and awareness among dairy cattle farmers regarding control practices of FMD (independent factor) and factors that influence their compliance to control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease (dependent factors)	7
Figure 2:Showing the study area.....	21
Figure 3:Showing farmers familiarity with Foot and mouth Disease and how the disease was first learnt about	32
Figure 4:Showing how often farmers-maintained cleanliness and disinfection of farm tools and equipment.....	41

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Showing sociodemographic information	29
Table 2: showing awareness and reported clinical signs of foot and mouth disease (FMD) among respondents.....	33
Table 3: showing foot and mouth disease control practices currently being implemented on the farm.....	35
Table 4: Showing who treated the sick animals as well as the reasons why farmers treated their own cattle	36
Table 5: showing factors that fail farmers to follow quarantine measures for the new cattle .	37
Table 6: showing how often farmers do vaccinate their cattle	39
Table 7: showing reasons why farmers do not vaccinate their cattle	40
Table 8: showing challenges to maintaining regular cleaning and disinfection practices	43
Table 9: showing challenges to accessing veterinary services	44
Table 10: showing challenges to compliance with foot and mouth disease control practices..	46

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ABBREVIATIONS	IN FULL
BSAL	Bachelor of Science in Agriculture and Livelihoods
DELSS	Department of Environment and Livelihood Support Systems
FIS	Faculty of Interdisciplinary Studies
FMD	Foot and Mouth Disease
FMDV	Foot and Mouth Disease Virus
MAAIF	Ministry of Agriculture, Animal Industry and Fisheries
MUST	Mbarara University of Science and Technology
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
UGX	Ugandan Shillings

ABSTRACT

Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) is a highly contagious viral infection that affects cloven-hoofed animals and continues to pose significant threats to dairy production more so in Uganda. This study aimed to (i) identify farmers' knowledge and awareness of FMD and its control practices, (ii) identify major factors influencing farmers' compliance with the control practices of Foot and Mouth disease and (iii) find out challenges hindering effective implementation of FMD control practices. A cross-sectional survey design was used, and data were collected from 100 dairy cattle farmers using semi-structured questionnaires. Respondents were categorized into small-, medium-, and large-scale farmers under an extensive dairy cattle production system. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods through SPSS Version 20. Findings showed that the majority (92%, N=100) of respondents were familiar with the disease. However, small-scale farmers mostly possessed knowledge about FMD (96.7%, n=30), followed by medium-scale farmers (92.5%, n=40), and then large-scale farmers (86.7%, n=30). Most farmers (90%, N=100) were aware of FMD control practices, with the majority being small-scale farmers (93.3%, n=30), followed by medium-scale farmers (92.5%, n=40), and lastly, large-scale farmers (83.3%, n=30). Key factors influencing compliance for (i) small scale farmers included; high costs of veterinary services (n=4/30), limited access to veterinary doctors (n=2/30), and inadequate government extension services (n=2/30) (ii) for medium-scale farmers included; limited availability and supply of vaccines (n=5/40) and inaccessibility of veterinary professionals (n=2/40) (iii) for large scale farmers included; inadequate quarantine facilities (n=7/30), high costs of veterinary services (n=6/30). Major challenges hindering their compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease control practices for (i) small scale farmers included; lack of access to vaccines (30.0%, n=9/30) and high medication and vaccination costs (23.3%, n=30) (ii) for medium scale farmers; high medication and vaccination costs and limited access to vaccines were the major (iii) for large scale farmers; limited access to sufficient vaccines (50.0%, n=30) and high medication and vaccination costs (10.0%, n=30) were also the major challenges. The study concludes that while the overall knowledge and awareness of FMD was high across all scales of production, the actual compliance to the practices was sub optimal due to economic, institutional and logistical challenges. The study recommends that (i) farmers should immediately report any suspected FMD cases to local veterinary authorities instead of informing fellow farmers, and strictly adhere to vaccination programs & biosecurity measures recommended by experts.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the background of the study, problem statement, objectives, scope, significance, justification and the conceptual framework of the study.

1.1 Background of the study

The dairy industry is one of the rapidly growing Agro-based industries worldwide, with an annual growth rate of approximately 2.5% to 3% (Kalaiselvi & Somasundaram, 2011). This remarkable growth has come about as a result of improved milk collection processes and the rising demand for livestock products driven by human population growth and rising incomes among milk consumers (Fuller et al., 2005). Additionally, the growth has been accelerated by an increase in the number of dairy cattle. This rise is mainly due to improved access to veterinary services, advanced breeding technologies, and the growing profitability of dairy farming (Waiswa & Günlü, 2023).

The growth of dairy industry has been noticed in almost all countries globally (Sarica et al., 2022). For instance milk production in Germany stood at approximately 33.3 million tons in 2020 experiencing a steady annual growth rate of around 1.4% from 2015 (Sauer & Latacz-Lohmann, 2020). In Thailand, milk production increased from 480,000 tons (2000) to approximately 1 million tons (2021), reflecting the ongoing expansion of the country's dairy industry (Garcia et al., 2021.) and in Uganda, the dairy industry continued to expand, with production increasing to approximately 2.5 million tons in 2021, reflecting a sustained annual growth rate of around 6% (Kusasira, 2023).

However, Foot and Mouth Disease is one of the economically significant diseases that have posed a significant threat to the dairy industry, with major outbreaks recorded in developing countries more so in Asia, Africa, the Middle East, and some regions of South America (Aslam & Alkheraije, 2023a). Foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) is a highly contagious viral disease that primarily affects cloven-hoofed animals, including cattle, pigs, sheep, goats, and other ruminants. The disease is caused by the Foot-and-Mouth Disease Virus (FMDV), which belongs to the Picornaviridae family and the genus Aphthovirus (Jamal & Belsham, 2013). According to the Food and Agriculture Organization, FMD has affected over 100 countries worldwide, leading to considerable economic losses estimated at between \$6.5 billion to \$21

billion annually due to decreased productivity, trade restrictions, and control measures (Pinto, 2017).

For instance, in Africa, FMD is widespread, with endemic pockets in sub-Saharan regions, particularly in East and Southern Africa (Thomson et al., 2014). A study by (Josiah et al., 2024) indicated that FMD outbreaks were recurrent in East African countries such as Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda, contributing to significant losses in livestock production and trade. In 2019, Africa recorded approximately 56% of the global FMD outbreaks, with notable incidences in regions engaged in trans boundary animal movement (Lazarus et al., 2021)

A 2020 report by the Ministry of Agriculture, Animal Industry, and Fisheries (MAAIF) indicated that Uganda experiences frequent outbreaks of FMD, with serotype O being the most prevalent, followed by SAT2 and A. Only in 2018, Uganda had over 1000 cases of FMD, affecting multiple districts such as Kiruhura, Mbarara, Nakaseke, and Kyankwanzi Districts along the cattle corridor zones (Okello et al., 2022). This caused significant losses in milk production, reduced cattle market prices, increased costs of vaccination and disease management, and reduced quantity of milk available to consumers for consumption (Baluka, et al., 2016)

Despite efforts to control the disease through vaccination and quarantine measures, challenges such as limited resources, inadequate veterinary services, and poor compliance with the control protocols still persist leading to increased spread of the disease to new areas, reduced productivity, and compromised food security (Kitching et al., 2005). The previous research has primarily concentrated on aspects such as vaccine efficacy (Wubshet et al., 2024), development of new vaccines (Balamurugan et al., 2012), and the economic impact of Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD) on livestock production (James & Rushton, 2003) with limited attention given to understanding the factors influencing farmers' compliance with the control practices.

This has created a gap in knowledge about the level of compliance with the control practices among farmers and the specific challenges they face in implementing these practices. However, if farmers are empowered with adequate knowledge and support regarding FMD control practices, they may be motivated to implement strategic biosecurity measures to prevent and control recurrent outbreaks of the disease thereby mitigating its economic impacts.

Therefore, the present study assessed the compliance of dairy cattle farmers with Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices in Byerima Sub County, Kyankwanzi District. This will generate sufficient information to bridge the identified gap identifying the factors

influencing compliance of dairy cattle farmers with FMD control practices, evaluating the level of knowledge and awareness among farmers, and identifying the challenges they face in implementing the recommended FMD control protocols.

Byerima Sub-County in Kyankwanzi District was selected for this study due to its prominent role in dairy farming within Uganda (Kirunda et al., 2012) and the frequent occurrence of FMD outbreaks in the region (Ahmed et al., 2022). This sub county's agricultural profile, combined with ongoing challenges in disease management and farmer compliance, provides a representative environment to explore and address the broader issues affecting FMD control in Uganda.

1.2 Problem statement

Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) is a persistent and significant challenge for the dairy industry, causing substantial economic losses and threatening the livelihoods of farmers (Knight-Jones et al., 2017). This problem is particularly critical in Uganda, where the dairy industry plays an essential role in agriculture by contributing to food security, providing employment, and generating income for millions of people (Chandio et al., 2017).

Even though the dairy industry is developing in Uganda due to increased adoption of modern farming techniques; better access to veterinary services; introduction of high-yielding cattle breeds; and increased demand for dairy products (Cheruiyot, 2017), the occurrence of FMD outbreaks continues to threaten the livelihoods of dairy farmers, with direct impacts on milk yield and quality, as well as increasing costs associated with disease management and control (Blake et al., 2009).

The existing research studies have concentrated on assessing the efficacy of the FMD vaccine and biosecurity measure implementation leaving a notable gap in understanding farmers compliance with recommended FMD control practices (Yaser et al., 2023). If this gap is not adequately addressed, the consequences will be severe including increased spread of the disease to new areas, reduced productivity, and compromised food security (Mazengia et al., 2010). Therefore, this study aimed to address this challenge by surveying to assess the dairy cattle farmers' compliance with control practices of foot and mouth disease in Byerima Sub-County kyankwanzi District by (i) finding out the major factors influencing the dairy cattle farmers' compliance with the control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease, (ii) identifying the level of knowledge and awareness among dairy cattle farmers regarding FMD and its control

practices and (iii) identifying the challenges hindering dairy cattle farmers from complying with control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease in Byerima Sub County kyankwanzi district.

1.3 Objectives of the study

This section outlines the general and specific objectives that guided the investigation into the research study topic.

1.3.1 General objective

To assess the dairy cattle farmers' compliance with the control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease in Byerima Sub County, Kyankwanzi District.

1.3.2 Specific objectives

- i) To identify the level of knowledge and awareness of FMD and its control practices among dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub County, Kyankwanzi District.
- ii) To find out the major factors influencing the dairy cattle farmers' compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease control practices.
- iii) To identify the challenges hindering dairy cattle farmers from complying with control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease.

1.4 Research questions

1. What is level of knowledge and awareness of FMD and its control practices among dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub County, Kyankwanzi District?
2. What are the major factors influencing the dairy cattle farmers' compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease control practices?
3. What are the challenges hindering dairy cattle farmers from complying with control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease?

1.5 Scope of the study

This dissertation lays out a proper and scientific strategy to assess the dairy cattle farmers' compliance with the control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease in Byerima Sub County kyankwanzi district. The study considered geographical, content, and time scopes to achieve its objectives.

1.5.1 Geographical scope of the study

The study was conducted within the boundaries of Byerima Sub County, which is situated in Kyankwanzi District, Central Uganda. Byerima Sub County is bordered to the north by the

Kiboga District, to the east by the Wattuba Sub County, to the west by the Nsambya Sub County, and to the south by the Ntwetwe Sub County within Kyankwanzi District. This sub county lies within the geographic coordinates of approximately 1.1500° N latitude and 31.5000° E longitude, encompassing a rural landscape predominantly characterized by agricultural and dairy farming activities.

1.5.2 Content scope of the study

The content scope of the research study encompassed a detailed examination of different aspects by focusing on (i) major factors influencing the dairy cattle farmers' compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease control practices, (ii) the level of knowledge and awareness of FMD control practices among dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub County, Kyankwanzi District, and (iii) identifying the challenges hindering dairy cattle farmers from complying with control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease.

The study also provided potential solutions and recommendations for the effective management of FMD. These aspects, taken together, formed a holistic approach that ensured a thorough examination of the compliance of dairy cattle farmers to control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease in Byerima Sub County, Kyankwanzi District.

1.5.3 Time scope of the study

This research covered a retrospective period of two years from January 2023 to December 2024. This time frame was chosen because Byerima sub-County in kyankwanzi District experienced repeated occurrences of Foot and Mouth Disease during those years. This allowed for an in-depth analysis of the partners, frequency, and impacts of FMD outbreaks on dairy cattle famers as well as the effectiveness of the implemented control measures over time.

1.6 Significance of the study

The study identified factors and challenges that prevented dairy cattle farmers from complying with Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices. This information will aid policymakers, veterinary service providers, and agricultural organizations in developing targeted interventions, such as educational programs to equip farmers with relevant knowledge and skills needed to fight against FMD outbreaks.

Farmers will directly benefit from this research by gaining access to practical knowledge and training on effective FMD control measures, leading to increased production of safe and healthier milk at a reduced cost of production, thus improving their livelihoods and food security. The study's findings will also help reduce the economic burden on farmers by

identifying cost-effective methods to prevent FMD outbreaks. Additionally, by increasing awareness and understanding of disease management, farmers will better be prepared to handle future outbreaks, ensuring the long-term sustainability of their farming operations.

Researchers will benefit by gaining detailed insights into the behavioral, economic, and logistical aspects that influenced compliance with FMD control practices. This knowledge will contribute to developing evidence-based strategies, enhancing scientific understanding of disease management, and guiding future research on animal health and epidemiology.

1.7 Justification of the study

Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) is a highly contagious viral disease that poses severe threats to the dairy industry, resulting in significant economic losses, reduced milk production, increased mortality, and compromised animal health and welfare. However, existing research on the implementation and effectiveness of Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control measures, such as vaccination programs, quarantine protocols, and biosecurity guidelines, has identified significant gaps in fully understanding the specific factors and challenges that hinder dairy farmers' compliance with these practices in Byerima Subcounty, Kyankwanzi District.

By addressing these gaps, this research will provide evidence-based recommendations to policymakers, veterinary service providers, and agricultural organizations, enabling them to design effective and responsive FMD control strategies that met the specific needs of dairy cattle farmers in the region. This, in turn, will reduce the frequency of outbreaks of the disease, improved herd health, and increased milk production among dairy cattle farmers. Additionally, the study will empower dairy farmers with the knowledge and resources necessary to effectively manage FMD and ensure sustainability and profitability of the dairy cattle sector.

1.8 Conceptual framework for the study

Figure 1 shows how the conceptualized variables (Farmer's awareness and knowledge; access to resources; and government support and policies) in the present study together with other intervening variables (farm size and type; experience in dairy farming; and frequency of disease outbreak) greatly influenced farmers' compliance with control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease (farmers' variables)

The farmers' decision to comply with or reject the Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices was postulated to be influenced by their beliefs derived from knowledge, perception, attitude and assessment of the technology or practice. For example, higher awareness and access to resources like vaccines and veterinary services enhanced compliance with the control

practices of the disease. However, intervening variables like farm size, farming experience, and outbreak frequency could either strengthen or weaken this compliance by affecting resource availability and disease management practices. Effective compliance with the control practices of foot and mouth disease led to desired outcomes like reduced FMD incidences, improved dairy productivity, enhanced livelihoods, and better market access.

Figure 1: showing the relationship between the level of knowledge and awareness among dairy cattle farmers regarding control practices of FMD (independent factor) and factors that influence their compliance to control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease (dependent factors)

Source: Developed by the researcher

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2 .0 Introduction

This chapter provides information about existing literature by other scholars regarding Foot and Mouth Disease as an economically important disease affecting cloven hooved livestock production. It is obtained from academic and research journals, working papers, and published research reports.

2.1 Dairy production

This section presents information on the current status of dairy production, the trends and drivers influencing it, and the various dairy production systems used in different parts of the world, based on insights from scholarly sources on dairy production.

2.1.1 Current status of dairy production

Milk production is a major agricultural activity worldwide, contributing to global food security, economic growth, and rural livelihoods (Rachael et al., 2022). The sector is prominent in regions like Europe, North America, South Asia, and Oceania, where large-scale operations dominate, while also supporting millions of smallholder farmers in developing countries (FAO, 2021).

2.1.2 Global milk production

Global milk production has experienced consistent growth, with North America, Europe, South Asia, and Oceania leading in output. North America, particularly the United States, produces over 100 billion liters annually, accounting for 14% of global milk production (FAO, 2021). In Europe, Germany and France contribute over 15% of the global total, focusing on milk and value-added dairy products such as cheese and butter (IDF, 2020). South Asia, led by India as the largest milk producer globally, generates more than 22% of total output, primarily from smallholder farms.

2.1.3 Milk production in Africa

Milk production in Africa is steadily growing, with countries like South Africa, Kenya, Ethiopia, and Sudan leading in output. South Africa's dairy industry is the most advanced, producing over 3 billion liters annually with a focus on large-scale commercial farming and modern processing facilities (FAO, 2022). In North Africa, Egypt contributes significantly, with milk production exceeding 5 billion liters annually, largely from buffalo and cattle (IDF,

2021). Ethiopia and Sudan, among the largest producers in Sub-Saharan Africa, rely heavily on pastoral and Agro-pastoral systems to supply domestic markets. In East Africa, Uganda leads with an annual production of about 5.3 billion liters, driven by smallholder farmers who account for 80% of the milk supply. Kenya follows with a rapidly growing sector, currently producing 5.2 billion liters annually, while Tanzania produces over 3.4 billion liters, supported by both smallholder and commercial dairy systems.

2.1.4 Milk production in Uganda

Uganda's milk production has experienced a remarkable growth in recent years, positioning the country as a leading milk producer in the East African region. Annual milk output rose by 53.4%, from 2.51 billion liters in 2018 to 3.85 billion liters in the 2022/2023 fiscal year, despite challenges such as drought in some areas (Ekou et al., 2023; Javira Ssebhwami et al., 2022). The Western region remains the highest contributor, accounting for 40% of total production, followed by the Central region at 34.3%, while the Northern region contributes only 3.7% (UBOS report, 2021). By June 2024, Uganda's annual milk production was estimated at 5.3 billion liters, with 80% of the milk marketed and 33% of that processed, while the rest is sold as raw milk.

2.1.5 Trends and drivers of dairy production

According to Food and Agriculture Organization report of 2021, the global dairy production has experienced consistent growth, increasing from 828 million metric tons in 2018 to 887 million metric tons in 2022, reflecting a 7.1% rise over four years. This growth was primarily driven by technological advancements, improved farming practices, and rising demand for dairy products across both developed and developing nations (Okello et al., 2021).

2.1.5.1 Milk output in developed countries

Developed regions such as Europe, North America, and Oceania account for the largest share of global milk output, with countries like the United States producing 102 billion liters annually. This increased production output is supported by efficient farming systems due to high levels of technology, supportive government policies and genetic improvements (USDA, 2022).

2.1.5.2 Dairy sector growth in Africa

Research conducted by Alemu et al. (2018) and Muriuki et al. (2021) highlighted that the growth of the dairy sector in African countries, particularly Kenya and Ethiopia, is driven by improvements in farming practices, technological adoption, and increasing demand for dairy

products. Alemu et al. (2018) emphasized the role of technological innovations in enhancing productivity, noting that Ethiopia's dairy production grew from 1.6 billion liters in 2010 to 2.4 billion liters annually by 2020, with plans to increase it to 4 billion liters by 2030.

2.1.5.3 Recent growth in Uganda's dairy industry

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO,2021) and Odeng et al. (2024), Uganda's dairy production has witnessed remarkable growth, rising from 1.8 billion liters in 2012 to an estimated 5.3 billion liters by 2024. This growth has been seen as a result of supportive government initiatives, including tax incentives for dairy farming inputs, along with significant investments in infrastructure and technology by the private sector (DDA, 2015).

2.2 Classification of dairy production systems globally

Globally, dairy production systems are categorized based on technological and economic development. In developed countries like India and North America, intensive dairy systems are the norm, involving large-scale, high-input operations with exotic breeds like Holsteins that produce high milk yields per cow. These systems are highly mechanized with advanced dairy management techniques. Conversely, in developing regions such as sub-Saharan Africa, extensive systems are more common, where local cattle breeds are kept on natural pastures, and milk production is lower, often supplemented by minimal or no concentrates (Ndambi et al., 2008).

2.2.1 Traditional classification of dairy systems

According to Okwenye et., 1994, the dairy production systems are classified into three groups, namely pastoral, small-scale crop and livestock farms and specialized dairy farms. This classification is based on number of stocks, feeding and grazing management and breeds reared.

2.2.2 Modern classification of dairy production systems

According to Ndambi et al., 2008 and FAO, 2019, the dairy production systems are categorized into intensive and extensive systems, which are further divided into the small scale and medium-sized extensive and intensive systems, large scale intensive systems, agropastoralist, and nomadic pastoralist systems depending on the size of herds, breeds of animals raised, grazing systems, annual milk production, and level of investment.

Mubiru et al. (2007), in their study on categorization of dairy production systems in Uganda, provided a framework for classifying dairy farms based on production intensity and herd size. They outlined systems such as the smallholder extensive system (System Four) with typically

fewer than 10 cattle, and the medium-holder extensive system (System Five) comprising farms with 10 to 20 cattle, which were managed with minimal external inputs but slightly improved husbandry practices. Similarly, a rapid appraisal conducted on the Kenyan dairy sub-sector (Omore et al., 1999) classified producers using broad production system indicators. The study recognized small-scale semi-intensive producers managing 1–20 animals, and large-scale extensive producers with more than 30 animals, largely composed of indigenous zebu breeds.

2.2.3 Characteristics of intensive vs. extensive dairy systems

Under the intensive production systems, farmers keep herds consisting of majorly exotic dairy cattle breeds, milk production per cow ranges from 2.4 to 2.7 tons per lactation and animal diets are usually supplemented with concentrate feeds. While under the extensive production systems, farmers keep herds consisting of majorly local cattle breeds with a few crosses, milk production per lactation ranges from 0.44 to 1.14 tons per lactation, and animals are grazed on natural pastures with minimal or no supplementation with concentrate feeds (Ndambi et al., 2008).

2.2.4 Milk production systems used in Uganda

According to Mbabazi et al., 2005, Milk production in Uganda operates through four main systems that is communal grazing, free-range grazing, fenced/paddock grazing, and zero-grazing. Communal grazing remains prevalent in Northern and Eastern Uganda, free-range grazing in Southern Uganda, Fenced/paddock grazing, typically used by farmers with smaller land holdings and Zero-grazing, primarily in Western Uganda which is supported by government programs and NGOs such as Send a Cow (UK) and Heifer International.

2.3 Challenges faced by the dairy sector

Despite registering significant levels of growth, the dairy industry continues to experience several challenges. According to the study by Waiswa et al. (2021), these challenges include the seasonality of milk production and consumption, unregulated informal milk markets, and unreliable formal markets compounded by high production costs, difficulties in animal breeding, climatic factors, and livestock diseases.

2.3.1 Limited infrastructures

While India maintains its top position in milk production, it lags behind developed nations such as the USA and Poland in terms of dairy farming efficiency and productivity. One of the key factors contributing to this gap is infrastructural limitations, such as inadequate chilling centers and the absence of an efficient cold chain distribution network, particularly at the village level.

These challenges hinder the smooth processing and transportation of milk, resulting in reduced overall efficiency in the dairy sector (Meena et al., 2017)

2.3.2 Genetic limitations of indigenous cattle in Ethiopia

In Ethiopia, one major technical challenge facing the dairy industry is the genetic limitation of the cattle population. Approximately 99% of Ethiopia's cattle are indigenous breeds, which are generally adapted to harsh climates, feed and water shortages, and disease challenges. However, their productivity is significantly lower compared to improved breeds (Waiswa et al., 2021).

2.3.3 Disease-related mortality and acaricide resistance

According to the study by Halima Abdallah 2019, Ugandan dairy industry faced the challenges of high mortality rates in exotic cattle, primarily caused by tick-borne diseases and the growing resistance of ticks to existing acaricides. This limited the industry's potential to increase annual export earnings from US\$100 million to an estimated US\$500 million despite the annual production which had risen to 2.4 billion liters.

2.4 Foot and Mouth Disease as an economically important disease on dairy cattle farms

This section presents the etiology, epidemiology, and signs and symptoms of foot and mouth disease as well as the risk factor that expose cattle to the disease.

2.4.1 Etiology of Foot and Mouth Disease

Foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) is caused by Foot-and-Mouth Disease Virus (FMDV) which belongs to the Picornaviridae family and the genus Aphthovirus. It is a highly contagious viral disease that primarily affects cloven-hoofed animals, including cattle, pigs, sheep, goats, and other ruminants (Abdullah Azeem et al., 2020a).

According to Abdullah Azeem et al., 2020, Foot-and-mouth disease virus (FMDV) is one of the earliest animal pathogens identified as a virus in the 16th century which is known for its complex epidemiology due to possession of seven distinct serotypes of FMDV: O, A, C, Asia1, SAT1, SAT2, and SAT3, with each serotype having multiple subtypes.

(Cottam, et al... 2008) reported that FMDV is a single-stranded, positive-sense RNA virus characterized by a sedimentation coefficient of 146S and a genome size of approximately 8.5 kilobases, which contributes to its ability to evolve rapidly and adapt to different hosts and environments.

2.4.2 Epidemiology of Foot and Mouth Disease

The epidemiology of foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) is influenced by a range of viral, host, and environmental factors, including virus virulence, particle stability, and the likelihood of long-term persistence (Ayelet et al., 2012).

According to the study by Carrillo, 2012, the primary site of infection and replication of Foot-and-Mouth Disease Virus (FMDV) is the mucosa of the pharynx, although the virus may also enter through skin lesions or the gastrointestinal tract. Upon entry, FMDV targets epithelial cells, particularly in the mouth and feet, leading to the formation of vesicles (blisters). These vesicles may rupture within 48 hours, resulting in painful ulcers, fever, lameness, and loss of appetite

FMD is highly transmissible and can spread through various pathways, including direct and indirect contact, ingestion, aerosols, and mechanical transmission. The virus infects animals via direct contact with infected individuals, contaminated materials (fomites), or through the air, particularly in temperate regions (Yoo, 2011).

The primary mode of transmission is through the movement of infected animals. However, FMDV can also spread indirectly via farm staff, vehicles, and animal products such as meat, milk, and semen (Muroga et al., 2013). Under specific weather conditions, FMDV can be transmitted by wind, as evidenced by an incident in 1981 where the virus traveled over 250 km from pigs in Brittany to infect cattle on the Isle of Wight (Donaldson et al., 1982).

The distribution of FMDV serotypes varies across endemic regions. Serotype O is responsible for around 70% of global FMD outbreaks and consists of two topotypes: East Africa-3 and West Africa. Serotype SAT2 belongs to a single topotype, VII, while Serotype A is classified under the topotype AFRICA/G-IV (Le et al., 2010). According to Munsey et al., 2019, six of the seven serotypes (O, A, C, SAT1, SAT2, SAT3) have been reported in Africa, four (O, A, C, Asia1) in Asia, and three (O, A, C) in South America in terms of geographical prevalence,

2.4.3 Signs and symptoms of dairy cattle suffering from foot and mouth disease

The FMD is considered as a notifiable disease (previously List A disease) of animals as per World Organization for Animal Health Office International des Epizooties (OIE) because of its high rate of transmissibility and imposition of international trade restrictions (Kumar et al., 2011).

According to Jamal & Belsham, (2013) and Abdullah Azeem et al., (2020a), the typical clinical sign is the development of vesicular lesions on the tongue, dental pad, gums, cheek, hard and soft palates, lips, nostrils, muzzle, interdigital region (between the hoof), and the coronary band. Other symptoms highlighted in the write-up include fever, which usually appears 24 to 48 hours before clinical signs develop.

A study by Yoo, (2011) indicated that animals infected with foot and mouth disease, may show additional symptoms to the clinical symptoms. Among the symptoms highlighted include depression, loss of appetite, weight loss, growth retardation, and a drop in milk production, which can persist even after recovery, were noted.

2.4.4 Risk factors that could predispose dairy cattle to foot and mouth disease

In the recent research on the risk factors contributing to the spread of foot-and-mouth disease Ilbeigi et al., (2018) reported that uncontrolled movement of animals, people, and equipment between farms is a significant factor, as the virus can be introduced through direct contact with infected animals or indirectly via contaminated equipment.

In the study on FMD transmission dynamics, Munsey et al., 2019, reported that introducing new animals to a herd without proper quarantine measures increases the risk of transmission, even if the animals appear healthy.

Furthermore,(Aslam & Alkheraije, 2023b), in their investigation of biosecurity practices in livestock farming, highlighted that inadequate cleaning of livestock facilities, equipment, and vehicles can harbor the FMD virus, and facilitate its spread.

2.4.5 Treatment of foot and mouth disease among dairy cattle famers

In regions that are normally FMD-free, control of the disease is typically attempted by culling all animals to reduce the risk of virus spread (Tildesley et al., 2009). Vaccination around outbreaks is also used to limit the spread of the disease in both normally FMD-free regions and endemic areas(Keeling et al., 2003)

Furthermore, movement restrictions are used during an outbreak to reduce the spread of disease, and more recently they have been used prior to an outbreak in order to change the structure of normal animal movement with the hope of limiting the size of future outbreaks (Velthuis & Mourits, 2007).

There is no specific treatment for FMD. However, conventional treatment methods are employed which involve the use of antibiotics, flunixin, Meglumine and mild disinfectants

(Radostitis et al. 2000). FMD has been managed traditionally by use of natural soda ash solution for washing of the lesions, while some communities have applied honey and even finger millet flour to the lesions (Gakuya et al. 2011).

Hedge et al. (2005) reported the application of cereals and honey for the treatment and control of foot and mouth disease. In their study, two farms fed animals 2 kg of cereal gruel daily for 20 days, a third for 10 days, and a fourth received none. All farms used a 1% KMnO₄ spray and honey-finger millet paste on wounds, which provided pain relief and healed wounds in three days, enabling cows to resume eating.

According to Ilbeigi et al., 2018, control of FMD in endemic regions such as Iran is mainly focused on mass vaccination of all susceptible livestock with a tetravalent vaccine, identification and testing of animals, establishment of protection and surveillance zones and enforcement of quarantine and biosecurity.

2.5 Level of knowledge and awareness among dairy cattle farmers regarding FMD and its control practices

In their study, Kafi et al. (2021) examined the socioeconomic factors influencing the level of awareness regarding FMD among dairy farmers in Iran and reported that farmers' education level, age, and access to veterinary services were strongly correlated with their knowledge of FMD. In this study, they found out that younger and more educated farmers with better access to veterinary services demonstrated higher awareness levels, emphasizing the need for tailored educational approaches to improve FMD management.

In Cambodia, a study conducted by Heng et al. (2019) highlighted significant deficiencies in knowledge and awareness among dairy cattle farmers regarding foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) control practices. The findings revealed a concerning trend in vaccination uptake, as over two-thirds of farmers reported not vaccinating their cattle during a two-year period from 2011 to 2013. Among those who did vaccinate, practices were inconsistent, characterized by irregular vaccination schedules and a lack of booster administration

According to the study by Nourani et al., 2021 in Afghanistan indicates that nearly half (48.5%) of farmers reported having heard of foot-and-mouth disease (FMD), with many able to identify common clinical signs such as salivation and lesions. However, this awareness does not always translate into effective disease management practices, as only a minority of farmers were aware of preventive measures or had participated in vaccination programs.

In a study conducted by Muriuki et al. (2022), on understanding Knowledge Gaps in Foot and Mouth Disease Control among Smallholder Dairy Farmers in East Africa, they noted that while farmers recognized FMD as a significant threat, their awareness of effective control measures, such as vaccination schedules and biosecurity practices, was limited.

In another study by Gikunda et al. (2020) on "Assessment of Farmers' Knowledge and Attitudes towards Foot and Mouth Disease in Kenya" it was found out that while most farmers were aware of FMD, their understanding of the disease's prevention and control practices was inadequate.

2.6 Factors influencing the compliance of dairy cattle farmers with control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease

According to Frössling and Nöremark (2016) and Toma et al. (2015), the level of technical knowledge possessed by farmers and veterinarians significantly affects their attitudes toward implementing biosecurity measures. Inadequate knowledge about disease transmission often leads to inconsistent control measures and gaps in knowledge can result in irregular vaccination schedules and insufficient booster administration.

2.6.1 Poor communication

Poor communication between animal health authorities and livestock producers has been identified as a key factor contributing to the spread of FMD. During the 2001 outbreaks in the UK and The Netherlands, inadequate and hastily crafted risk communication led to confusion and decreased trust in the disease control process (Kostova-Vassilevska, 2004).

According to Broughan et al. (2016), farmers' experiences with FMD significantly impact their compliance with the control practices of FMD. Those who have faced FMD outbreaks are more likely to adopt preventive measures very first as compared to those who have not experienced it due to past economic losses and the complexities of managing the disease.

2.6.2 Source of information

Farmers with access to reliable sources of information, such as veterinary services and extension programs, are more knowledgeable about FMD and more likely to follow control measures (Laanen et al., 2014). Additionally, the characteristics of the farm, such as size and location, and personal attributes like age and gender, have also been reported to affect the willingness of farmers to invest in biosecurity (Hoe & Ruegg, 2006; Sayers et al., 2013).

According to Kristensen and Jakobsen (2011), Positive interactions with veterinary services build trust and cooperation in disease control efforts. However, bureaucratic inefficiencies and perceived obstacles within veterinary services can lead to reliance on informal networks for disease management (Hovi et al., 2005).

According to the study by Cardwell et al., 2016 it was reported that compliance with foot and mouth disease control practices depended on observing peers or community leaders adopting biosecurity measures where by some other famers complied with the practices having seen their peers practicing them.

2.6.3 High cost of vaccines

Brennan and Christley 20120 observed that the cost of vaccines and biosecurity practices can be prohibitive for many farmers, leading to low vaccination rates and inadequate biosecurity implementation. Pritchard et al. (2015) emphasized that the time and labor required for these measures contribute to the economic burden, influencing farmers' compliance.

2.7 Challenges hindering dairy cattle farmers from complying with the control practices of Foot and Mouth

This section outlines the challenges faced by dairy cattle farmers in relation to different studies carried out by different scholars.

2.7.1 Socio-Cultural and knowledge-based constraints

Singh and Chander (2005) studied the FMD vaccination status of milch cattle and buffalo in Bareilly and reported that illiteracy among farmers, myth related to after-effects of vaccination and lack of infrastructure were the constraints faced by doctors in implementing successful vaccination programme. Twenty percent doctors said that due to cost factor involved, farmers did not come forward for vaccination and 49.16% respondents reported the lack of money to afford vaccine cost.

2.7.2 Financial and Economic Barriers

In their study on 'economic and livelihood constraints of biosecurity measures on farms', Brennan and Christley (2012) highlighted economic constraints, such as the cost of vaccination and biosecurity measures, and high transportation costs to secure vaccines from the veterinary service providers as significant barriers for many farmers. Additionally, time constraints and the perceived complexity of implementing these measures can result in non-compliance (Pritchard et al., 2015).

2.7.3 Limited knowledge and awareness of the vaccine

In assessment of the constraints and adoption of peste des petits ruminant's vaccination among livestock farmers, Saliu et al. (2008) reported that inadequate knowledge of the vaccine was the major constraint in adopting peste des petits ruminants (PPR) vaccine, the extra cost for locating the veterinary agents, unavailability and the high cost of vaccines were the other major constraints reported by the same researchers.

2.7.4 Poor communication

Roy et al. (2006) reported the communication gap to be a major constraint hindering farmers from complying food and mouth disease control practices. Other constraints reported by them were the long distance to the veterinary hospitals, lack of faith in modern veterinary medicines, high cost of treatment and relying heavily on indigenous methods.

2.7.5 Institutional and Organizational Constraints

According to Kristensen and Jakobsen (2011), the relationship between farmers and veterinary authorities influences the compliance to the control practices of FMD. They found that organizational support, as well as the perceived bureaucracy within veterinary systems, can either facilitate or hinder farmers' compliance with biosecurity practices.

Similarly, Hovi et al. (2005) highlight that excessive bureaucracy often leads to frustration among farmers, impacting their willingness to cooperate with veterinary guidelines. Furthermore, Heffernan et al. (2008) emphasized that a lack of trust in formal reporting channels can push farmers to rely on informal networks for disease management information.

2.7.6 Limited compensation of the lost animals

According to Spear (1982), the historical account of the 1924 foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) outbreak in California highlights significant challenges in securing farmer cooperation during disease control efforts. Spear's research, titled "The 1924 Outbreak of Foot-and-Mouth Disease in California: Lessons in Disease Control," reveals that two primary obstacles emerged: the lack of adequate funding for compensating farmers for livestock losses and the absence of legal authority to cull uninfected but potentially exposed animals. These constraints led to substantial resistance from livestock producers, who were unwilling to fully comply with disease control measures

2.7.7 Unavailability of veterinary service providers

According to Mavi et al. (2006), in their study titled "Constraints in the Adoption of Improved Dairy Farming Practices by Dairy Farmers of Punjab," the unavailability of veterinary services

during nighttime emerged as a significant barrier to effective dairy farming. Their research reported that 54.29 percent of the respondents identified this issue as a major constraint hindering them from complying with the control practices effectively

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3 .0 Introduction

This chapter presents the research methods that were used in this study. They include the research design, study population, sample size, sampling techniques, data collection methods and tools, data analysis, limitations and delimitations, and ethical considerations.

3.1 Study area description

Kyankwanzi District is situated in the central part of Uganda, 140 kilometers (87 miles) from Kampala city, at an elevation of approximately 1,200 to 1,300 meters above sea level. This elevation gives it a mild, subtropical climate favorable for agriculture. The district is bordered by Nakaseke District to the East, Kiboga District to the South, Kiryandongo District to the North, and Hoima District to the West (Bahk et al., 2018).

Kyankwanzi District is divided into several administrative units, including Sub-Counties and town councils, with Butemba Sub-County serving as the district's capital. Other notable administrative divisions include the Wattuba Sub-county to the east, Nsambya Sub-county to the west, and Ntwetwe Sub-county to the south (Kisame et al.,2009).

The study was conducted in Byerima Sub- County, located in Butemba County, Kyankwanzi District in Central Uganda. This Sub- County was particularly chosen as the study area because it is one of the regions most affected by Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) outbreaks in Kyankwanzi District (Kyankwanzi District Veterinary Office, 2023), despite its ability to produce significant amounts of milk that contribute to food availability in the area. The sub county also has a rich network of dairy farmers, providing a suitable population for studying compliance of dairy cattle famers with the control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease.

3.1.1 Map of Uganda showing the study location of Byerima sub county, Kyankwanzi district, central Uganda.

Figure 2: Showing the study area

Source: Kisame et al.,2009)

3.2 Research design

The study employed a cross-sectional study design in assessing dairy cattle farmers' compliance with the control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease in Byerima Sub County, Kyankwanzi District. This design was selected as the most suitable because it allowed for the collection of data at a single point in time and facilitated an in-depth analysis of the factors influencing compliance with FMD control practices and challenges to compliance with FMD.

3.3 Study population

In this study, the target population comprised of only dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub-County, Kyankwanzi District, categorized into small-scale, medium-scale, and large-scale dairy cattle farmers who employed an extensive livestock production system. This system was

selected because it was predominant in the study area and presented unique challenges for managing dairy cattle health and productivity, including limited control over grazing conditions and disease exposure. According to this study, the small-scale farmers included those owning 1 to 20 dairy cattle, the medium-scale farmers consisted of those owning 21 to 50 dairy cattle, and the large-scale farmers included those owning 51 and above dairy cattle.

Other small-scale dairy cattle farmers using semi-intensive and intensive production systems were excluded from this study because their controlled management practices, such as confined feeding and restricted grazing, reduce the risks associated with disease exposure and grazing conditions. Consequently, these systems present different challenges and health dynamics compared to those found in the extensive livestock production system predominant in the study area.

3.4 Sampling

This section covered the sampling size and sampling techniques used in studying dairy cattle farmers' compliance with FMD control practices in Byerima sub county kyankwanzi district.

3.4.1 Sample size determination

The formula used in determining the sample size in this study was adopted from (Barlett et al., 2001), which is given as $N = \frac{4pq}{L^2}$, where **N** represents the total size of the sample; **P** represents the probability of finding a respondent at home; **Q** represents the probability of not finding a respondent at home and **L** represents the error margin.

Using the probability of finding a respondent at home as 50%, then;

$$P=0.5, q= (1-p), L=0.1$$

$$N = \frac{4(0.5)(0.5)}{(0.1)^2}$$

Therefore, the number of respondents selected for the survey was 100. Among these respondents, 30 were small-scale dairy farmers, 40 were medium-scale dairy farmers, and 30 were large-scale dairy farmers. This distribution ensured a balanced representation across different scales of dairy farming, enabling thorough analysis and comparison of factors affecting dairy cattle farmers' compliance with the control practices for Foot and Mouth Disease.

3.4.2 Sampling techniques and procedure

Cluster, purposive and simple random sampling techniques were utilized to select samples for this study. In the first stage the Sub- County was first divided into parishes using a cluster sampling technique. Among the formed parishes, a parish with the highest number of dairy cattle farmers was selected purposively. Within this parish, the selected dairy cattle farmers were then stratified into groups of small-scale, medium-scale, and large-scale farmers based on their farm sizes and finally simple random sampling was employed to select study participants from each group.

3.5 Data collection

Data collection involved both primary and secondary data sources to gather comprehensive information on famers' compliance with the control practices of Foot and Mouth Disease.

3.5.1 Methods of data collection

The required information for this study was obtained through the collection of both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected using self-administered structured questionnaires within the framework of a survey research method. These questionnaires were designed to collect respondents' views on the subject matter in a consistent and systematic manner.

The self-administered questionnaires were distributed directly to the respondents, who were asked to complete them independently. This method allowed participants to provide their responses at their own pace and convenience, promoting honest and thoughtful answers. However, in cases where some respondents were unable to read or write, the researcher provided assistance by reading the questions aloud, explaining them where necessary, and recording the responses on behalf of the participants. This ensured inclusivity and minimized response bias due to literacy barriers.

3.5.1.1 Primary data

Quantitative primary data was collected from dairy cattle farms through self-administered questionnaires and structured surveys. These questionnaires were personally distributed to selected dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub-County and were designed to gather numerical data on farmers' knowledge, awareness, and compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices. Respondents were guided on how to complete the forms, and where necessary particularly in cases involving illiterate farmers, the researcher read the questions aloud, interpreted them and recorded their responses.

3.5.1.2 Secondary data

Secondary data was collected by reviewing relevant literature before and during the study from magazines, newspapers, the internet, journals, publications, documentaries, and reports, especially from the Kyankwanzi District Production Department and the Ministry of Agriculture, Animal Industry, and Fisheries, (MAAIF) among others. This provided insights into the study topic based on the contributions of other researchers and authors.

3.5.2 Tools of data collection

The study employed the use of semi-structured questionnaires (Appendix i), books and pens to collect accurate and reliable data.

3.6 Data Analysis

Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as means, frequencies, and percentages, along with inferential statistics, including chi-square tests, to examine the relationship between compliance with foot and mouth disease control practices and other factors.

Data was securely stored under lock and key to prevent loss and then entered into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 20) for statistical analysis. Biographic data was described using frequency and percentage levels, and objectives were analyzed to generate tables, pie charts, and histograms.

3.7 Ethical Considerations

The study was first approved by the Faculty of Interdisciplinary Studies (FIS) at Mbarara University of Science and Technology (MUST), which issued an introductory letter (Appendix iii) to allow data collection from the field. The approval ensured that the study or data collection techniques used in the field were ethically right and that the study followed ethical principles including respect for participants, justice, beneficence, and non-maleficence. Informed consent (Appendix ii) was sought from all participants, who were assured of the confidentiality of their responses through anonymized codes. Participants were informed that their involvement was voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time, and all collected data were securely stored.

3.8 Limitations and Delimitation

This section presents the limitations which hindered the researcher from conducting the study and or obtain accurate and reliable data from the field together with the delimitations.

3.8.1 Limitations

The study was limited by the inaccessibility of some remote farmers, limited response rates due to the busy schedules of dairy farmers, language barriers, and the exclusion of certain variables due to financial or technological constraints, which impacted the depth of data collection and the reliability of the results depending on the accuracy of the collected data.

3.8.2 Delimitations

While maintaining a primary focus on Byerima Sub-County, collaboration with researchers or institutions in other regions was pursued to enhance the study's applicability. To address the time frame limitation, the study considered extending its duration and conducting follow-ups to capture long-term trends. The inclusion of various farm scales, from small to large operations, was prioritized to offer a nuanced understanding of how foot and mouth disease affected different scales of dairy cattle farms. Efforts were made to overcome language limitations by collaborating with translators fluent in relevant languages to include valuable non-English sources and perspectives.

CHAPTER FOUR

PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION, AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4 .0 Introduction

This chapter outlines data presentation and interpretation described using pie charts, graphs (line and bar graphs), and tables. Data was analyzed based on statistics from the structured questionnaires of the respondents during data collection. The data was presented, analyzed, and interpreted according to the objectives.

4.1 Socio-demographic characteristics

This study revealed that extensive dairy cattle production in Byerima Subcounty, Kyankwanzi District was largely male-dominated (75.0%, N=100) across all scales of production. The highest concentration of male farmers was observed in small scale -scale and large-scale farms each with (76.7%, n=30), indicating that men are more actively engaged or take leadership roles in dairy farming, especially at the small scale and large-scale level of production.

These findings contradict those of Ampaire et al. (2020), who reported that male dominance in dairy farming was more pronounced at the semi-commercial and medium-scale levels, rather than at small- and large-scale levels, in Uganda's central cattle corridor. Likewise, Nabukenya et al. (2017), in their gender analysis of livestock value chains, found that male leadership was more characteristic of medium-scale farming households, which they linked to traditional gender norms, land ownership, and men's greater access to capital and extension services.

The majority of respondents were married (95.0%, N=100) and aged between 41–50 years (43.0%, N=100) with the majority being the large-scale farmers (50.0%, n=30). This suggests that dairy cattle production is largely managed by a mature and stable group of farmers. This finding is supported by Mugisha et al. (2014), who found that dairy farmers in central Uganda were predominantly married individuals in the 40–50-year age group, a demographic often associated with settled households, land ownership, and long-term agricultural engagement. Additionally, Wanyoike et al. (2015), in a study on dairy farmers in East Africa, noted that the most active age group in dairy farming ranged between 40 and 55 years, coinciding with peak working capacity, accumulated farming knowledge, and greater access to productive assets.

Educational attainment was generally low, with primary education being most common (N=44/100), particularly among medium-scale producers (n=19/40), which may affect understanding and compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices. This

finding is in agreement with findings by Lapar et al. (2003) in Vietnam, who reported that most small- and medium-scale dairy farmers had only primary-level education, which limited their ability to comprehend and adopt improved livestock management and disease control practices. Similarly, Sambo et al. (2017) in Nigeria also observed that primary education was predominant among dairy producers, especially those operating at medium and small scales, affecting their responsiveness to veterinary guidelines and disease prevention programs.

Most respondents had over 10 years of farming experience (41.0%; N=100), especially in medium-scale farms (45.0%, n=40), suggesting extensive practical knowledge, though not necessarily aligned with modern disease control standards. This finding aligns with the results of Mangesho et al. (2017) in Tanzania, who reported that a majority of dairy farmers had over a decade of farming experience, particularly among medium-scale producers, yet showed limited compliance with recommended biosecurity practices due to a reliance on traditional knowledge.

Some (N=59/100) of the farmers owned farms, and farm ownership was slightly higher among medium-scale farmers (n=26/40), likely contributing to better commitment to FMD control. This indicates that ownership may foster a stronger sense of responsibility and investment in maintaining effective disease control measures on the farm. This finding is consistent with those of Alhaji and Odetokun (2013) in Nigeria, who observed that medium-scale livestock farmers owned their production units compared to small-scale farmers, attributing this trend to increased access to land, capital, and long-term investment in animal production. Similarly, Chatikobo et al. (2014) in Zimbabwe found that farm ownership was predominantly observed among farmers in the mid-tier scale of production, who had more stable operations and were more likely to secure land tenure for livestock farming.

Roles at the farm varied, with farm managers (15.0%, N=100) being the majority in large-scale farms (20.0%, n=30) while technical roles like farm doctors (5.0%, N=100) were few, especially in large-scale farms (3.3%, n=30). This indicates that management roles are more prevalent, while specialized technical roles, which are critical for effective disease control and farm health, are underrepresented. This finding aligns with that of Muriuki (2011), who found that large-scale dairy farms in Kenya were predominantly managed by farm managers, with technical roles such as veterinarians or animal health specialists being less common. Similarly, a study by Ahmed et al. (2019) in India reported that large-scale dairy farms in the Punjab

region had farm managers overseeing day-to-day operations, while veterinarians or trained animal health experts were few, especially in the less commercially developed regions.

All participants (N=100/100) in all scales of production practiced extensive production systems, which pose significant risk for FMD spread due to communal grazing. The findings show that dairy cattle production was the major source of income for the majority (N=85/100) of respondents across all scales of extensive production, with the highest proportion in large-scale farms (n=27/30). This indicates that despite variations in production scale, dairy remains a key economic activity, particularly for large-scale farmers who rely more heavily on it for their livelihood. This observation is strongly supported by Asimwe et al. (2020), who found that in Uganda's central cattle corridor, large-scale dairy farmers derived most of their household income from milk sales, often using earnings to meet essential needs such as school fees, medical care, and reinvestment in farm inputs. Similarly, Mwebesa et al. (2015) reported that large-scale dairy farmers in Mbarara and Kiruhura districts relied more intensively on dairy than both small-scale and medium-scale producers.

Other respondents who did not rely on dairy production as their main income, crop growing (N=9/100) was the most cited alternative, particularly among small-scale farmers (n=4/30). This reflects the continued importance of crop farming as a supplementary or fallback livelihood option, especially for smallholders with limited dairy output. This finding is supported by Turyahikayo et al. (2018), who observed that smallholder dairy farmers in western Uganda often engaged in subsistence or semi-commercial crop farming as a buffer against the unpredictability of livestock-based incomes. Similarly, Nabikolo et al. (2014), in a study on rural livelihood strategies in Uganda, found that mixed farming systems combining dairy and crops were most common among small-scale farmers, who typically lacked sufficient herd sizes or market access to sustain their households from milk alone.

Regarding the contribution of dairy to total household income, a moderate contribution was most frequently reported (N=53/100), especially in medium-scale farms (n=23/40), while high contribution (N=40/100) was most common among the large-scale producers (n=14/30). This implies that large-scale farmers benefit significantly from dairy, whereas small-scale farmers may face limitations in scale and profitability.

This finding aligns with Katongole et al. (2017) in Uganda, who reported that large-scale dairy farms in the southwestern region experienced higher profitability due to larger herd sizes, better market access, and more consistent milk yields. In contrast, small-scale farms often struggled

with limited production and poor milk quality, reducing their economic gains. Similarly, García et al. (2007), in a study of smallholder dairy systems in Latin America, highlighted that smaller farm often faced structural and financial barriers, including limited land, fewer cows, and low productivity per animal, resulting in less significant income contribution from dairy compared to larger farms.

Other income sources were diverse and depended significantly on the production scale: small-scale farmers mainly engaged in crop growing (63.3%, n=30), medium-scale farmers dominated in selling animals and their products (45.0%, n=40), while large-scale farmers had greater participation in renting houses (20%, n=30). This highlights that income diversification patterns align with resource availability and investment capacity across scales small-scale farmers rely more on agriculture, medium-scale on livestock trade, and large-scale on asset-based income.

This finding is consistent with Benin et al. (2008) in Uganda, who found that resource-constrained smallholders engaged mostly in subsistence crop farming alongside livestock keeping to meet household food needs and generate minimal income. In contrast, Bebe et al. (2003) in Kenya observed that medium-scale dairy farmers sold surplus livestock and livestock products, as they had larger herds and better market orientation. Additionally, De Vries (2008) reported similar trends in Ethiopia, where wealthier livestock farmers diversified into non-agricultural income streams such as real estate, transport, and poultry, using their capital to invest in asset-based ventures that offer higher returns and reduced dependency on unpredictable agricultural markets. Other socio-demographic characteristics of farmers are indicated in table 1.

Table 1: Showing sociodemographic information

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total frequency N=100	Total (%)
		Small scale (n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale(n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Gender of respondents	M	23.0	76.7	29.0	72.5	23.0	76.7	75.0	100.0
	F	7.0	23.3	11.0	27.5	7.0	23.3	25.0	100.0
Age range	41-50	11.0	36.7	17.0	42.5	15.0	50.0	43.0	100.0
	31-40	10.0	33.3	11.0	27.5	9.0	30.0	30.0	100.0
	51-60	7.0	23.3	10.0	25.0	5.0	16.7	22.0	100.0
	21-30	2.0	6.7	1.0	2.5	1.0	3.3	4.0	100.0
	Greater than 60	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0

Marital status	Married	28.0	93.3	38.0	95.0	29.0	96.7	95.0	100.0
	Single	2.0	6.7	2.0	5.0	1.0	3.3	5.0	100.0
Education level	Primary	13.0	43.3	19.0	47.5	12	40.0	44.0	100.0
	Secondary	7.0	23.3	13.0	32.5	9.0	30.0	29.0	100.0
	Bachelors	2.0	6.7	3.0	7.5	6.0	20.0	11.0	100.0
	Certificate	3.0	10.0	3.0	7.5	2.0	6.7	8.0	100.0
	Diploma	5.0	16.7	2.0	5.0	1.0	3.3	8.0	100.0
Farm ownership	Yes	16.0	53.3	26.0	65.0	17.0	56.7	59.0	100.0
	No	14.0	46.7	14.0	35.0	13.0	43.3	41.0	100.0
Role at the farm	Farm worker	3.0	10.0	8.0	20.0	5.0	16.7	16.0	100.0
	Farm manager	6.0	20.0	3.0	7.5	6.0	20.0	15.0	100.0
	Farm doctor	3.0	10.0	1.0	2.5	1.0	3.3	5.0	100.0
	Assistant Farm Manager	2.0	6.7	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	3.0	100.0
	Feed Formulator	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.3	1.0	100.0
	Poultry specialist	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
Years of engagement in dairy cattle production	Over 10 years	13.0	43.3	18.0	45.0	10.0	33.3	41.0	100.0
	6-10 years	8.0	26.7	10.0	25.0	11.0	36.7	29.0	100.0
	1-5 years	7.0	23.3	9.0	22.5	8.0	26.7	24.0	100.0
	Less than one year	2.0	6.7	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	3.0	100.0
	20 years	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	1.0	3.3	2.0	100.0
	30 years	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
Livestock productions system	Extensive	30.0	100.0	40.0	100.0	30.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Was dairy cattle production the major source of income	Yes	22.0	73.3	36.0	90.0	27.0	90.0	85.0	100.0
	No	8.0	26.7	4.0	10.0	3.0	10.0	15.0	100.0
Major source of income in 2023 and 2024 if not dairy	Crop growing	4.0	13.4	2.0	5.0	3.0	10.0	9.0	100.0
	Poultry keeping	2.0	6.7	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	3.0	100.0
	Renting houses	1.0	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
	Selling banana	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
	veterinary drug shop	1.0	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
Contribution of dairy income on overall income	Moderate contribution	15.0	50.0	23.0	57.5	15.0	50.0	53.0	100
	High contribution	12.0	40.0	14.0	35.0	14.0	46.7	40.0	100.0
	Low contribution	3.0	10.0	3.0	7.5	1.0	3.3	7.0	100.0
Other sources of income at home	Selling animals and their products	6.0	20.0	18.0	45.0	8.0	26.7	32.0	100.0
	Crop growing	19.0	63.3	0.0	0.0	8.0	26.7	27.0	100.0
	Renting houses	0.0	0.0	6.0	15.0	6.0	20.0	12.0	100.0
	Poultry keeping	2.0	6.7	5.0	12.5	5.0	16.7	12.0	100.0
	Shop keeping	1.0	3.3	4.0	10.0	1.0	3.3	6.0	100.0
	Apiculture	0.0	0.0	4.0	10.0	1.0	3.3	5.0	100.0
	Selling food crops	0.0	0.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	3.3	3.0	100.0
	Selling preserved pastures	2.0	6.7	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	3.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

4.2 Knowledge and awareness of FMD and its control practices among dairy cattle farmers

4.2.1 Familiarity with Foot and Mouth Disease

The findings from the current study, as shown in figure 3 show that the majority of the dairy cattle farmers (92.0%, N=100) in Byerima Sub-County reported being familiar with Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD). Among these, small-scale farmers constituted the largest proportion (96.7%, n=30), followed by medium-scale producers (92.5%, n=40). This high level of familiarity is likely a result of frequent FMD outbreaks in the region, its significant economic impact, and the farmers' interaction with veterinary professionals.

These findings are consistent with a study by Kafi et al. (2021) in Iran, which reported that 85% of dairy farmers had heard of FMD, with awareness highest among medium-scale farmers a pattern also seen in the present study. Similarly, Muriuki et al. (2022) in Kenya found over 90% FMD awareness, especially in areas with recurrent outbreaks, although they highlighted a gap between awareness and in-depth understanding of control measures. In contrast, studies conducted in Cambodia (Heng et al., 2019) and Afghanistan (Nourani et al., 2021) reported much lower awareness levels of 58% and 48.5%, respectively. These differences were attributed to weak veterinary extension systems and fewer outbreak experiences

Other respondents (8.0%; N=100) indicated unfamiliarity with the disease, a minority that may be attributed to factors such as limited exposure, smaller herd sizes, or weaker engagement with veterinary services. This finding is consistent with observations by Nyaguthii et al. (2019) in Kenya, where a small proportion of smallholder farmers were similarly unaware of FMD, often due to minimal herd sizes, remote locations, and low interaction with veterinary personnel.

The majority of dairy cattle farmers (57.0%, N=100) reported that their primary source of information on Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) were veterinary professionals more so among large-scale farmers (63.3%, n=30). These findings are in line with Kristensen and Jakobsen (2011), who found that farmers maintaining regular, trusting relationships with veterinary personnel in East Africa received timely and accurate FMD information and complied with recommended control measures than their counterparts.

Media sources (6.0%, N=100) was the least used source of information across all scales of production with the majority of the users being the small-scale farmers (10.0%, n=30). The

relatively low reliance on media sources aligns with Nourani et al. (2021), who found similar trends in Afghanistan, attributing them to factors such as low literacy, limited network coverage, and language barriers in rural farming communities. This points to broader infrastructural challenges in utilizing mass media for veterinary education in such settings. Similarly, Cardwell et al. (2016) found out that farmers adopted biosecurity practices when trusted peers endorsed them publicly supporting the significance of the 19.0% of Byerima farmers who received FMD information through fellow farmers.

Figure 3: Showing farmers familiarity with Foot and mouth Disease and how the disease was first learnt about

Source: Field data, 2025

4.2.2 Knowledge of respondents on the signs and symptoms of Foot and mouth disease in cattle

The study revealed that all respondents (N=100/100) were able to identify Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) symptoms, demonstrating a high level of awareness within Byerima subcounty. The most frequently cited symptom included wounds in the mouth and on the tongue (N=19/100) reported mostly by the medium scale farmers (n=10/40). Other reported symptoms included salivation and lameness as shown in Table 2. These findings closely correspond with those of Jamal and Belsham (2013), who documented that hallmark FMD symptoms such as salivation, vesicle formation in the mouth and on the feet, and subsequent lameness are widely recognized by farmers in endemic regions, including those without formal veterinary training.

The universal recognition of these symptoms in the present study aligns with these established clinical patterns typically observed in high-risk areas.

Similarly, Gikunda et al. (2020) reported that 87% of dairy farmers in Kenya could correctly identify FMD symptoms, with previous personal or community outbreak experience. Further supporting this, Yoo (2011) observed that visible signs such as blisters, salivation, fever, and lameness were commonly and easily identified by farmers, even outside formal veterinary systems. He noted that while some signs, like reduced milk yield and growth retardation, may be less immediately obvious, experienced farmers in endemic areas tend to recognize them as part of the disease pattern.

Table 2: showing awareness and reported clinical signs of foot and mouth disease (FMD) among respondents

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq) N	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Whether they know the symptoms of FMD	Yes	30.0	100.0	40.0	100.0	30.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Reported symptoms of FMD	Wounds in the mouth and on the tongue	7.0	23.3	10.0	25.0	2.0	6.7	19.0	100.0
	Excess salivation	6.0	20.0	5.0	12.5	6.0	20.0	17.0	100.0
	Loss of appetite	1.0	3.3	6.0	15.0	9.0	30.0	16.0	100.0
	Wounds between hooves	7.0	23.3	4.0	10.0	4.0	13.4	15.0	100.0
	Lameness	2.0	6.7	5.0	12.5	3.0	10.0	10.0	100.0
	High body temperatures	0.0	0.0	3.0	7.5	4.0	13.3	7.0	100.0
	Low milk yields	2.0	6.7	3.0	7.5	0.0	0.0	5.0	100.0
	Abortions	1.0	3.3	3.0	7.5	0.0	0.0	4.0	100.0
	Weight loss	2.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.3	3.0	100.0
	Body weakness	2.0	6.7	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	3.0	100.0
Standing far on the body	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.3	1.0	100.0	

Source: Field data, 2025

4.3 Awareness of the FMD control practices recommended by veterinary authorities

The findings from the current study revealed that the majority of dairy farmers (90%, N=100) in Byerima Sub-County were aware of the Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices recommended by veterinary authorities with small-scale farmers (93.3%, n=30) constituting the largest proportion of those reporting awareness, followed by medium scale farmers (92.5%, n=40). This suggests that small-scale farmers may have better access to veterinary information and services, possibly due to their small herd sizes that necessitate more frequent engagement with animal health professionals compared to medium-scale or even some large-scale operators.

These results are consistent with findings by Muriuki et al. (2022), who conducted a study in Kenya and Uganda and reported that over 85% of farmers were aware of FMD control practices such as vaccination, disinfection, and animal quarantining but showed a discrepancy between awareness and consistent implementation of these practices, especially in resource-limited farming systems. Similarly, Frössling and Nöremark (2016) reported in Sweden that although farmers were generally knowledgeable about biosecurity and livestock disease control, their application of these practices was shaped by economic constraints, disease risk perception, and trust in veterinary authorities.

On the other hand, the minority of the dairy cattle farmers (10%, N=100) were not aware of the recommended control practices with the majority being the large-scale farmers (16.7%, n=30). This finding contradicts the results of Gakuya et al. (2011) in central Kenya, who reported that large-scale dairy producers exhibited significantly higher awareness and adoption of disease control measures, including those for FMD, due to their access to formal training, veterinary networks, and structured farm management systems.

Fencing the farm to restrict movement (27%, N=100) was the most common control practice reported by the dairy cattle farmers, with the majority being the small-scale farmers (40.0%, n=30). This finding contradicts the observations of Sieng et al. (2021) in Cambodia, who reported that the most common response to FMD outbreaks among smallholder farmers was immediate treatment of clinically affected animals, rather than implementation of preventive biosecurity measures like fencing. In their study, 57% of farmers assisted others in restraining and treating sick animals even before their own cattle were infected, and 43% did so after infection, reflecting a communal, reactive approach. Other reported control practices employed in Byerima subcounty are shown in the table 3 below.

Table 3: showing foot and mouth disease control practices currently being implemented on the farm

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Awareness about the recommended FMD control practices	Yes	28.0	93.3	37.0	92.5	25.0	83.3	90.0	100.0
	No	2.0	6.7	3.0	7.5	5.0	16.7	10.0	100.0
Recommended FMD control practices being implemented currently	Fencing the farm to restrict movement	12.0	40.0	10.0	25.0	5.0	16.7	27.0	100.0
	Farm sanitation and disinfection	7.0	23.3	10.0	25.0	2.0	6.7	19.0	100.0
	Isolation and quarantine	5.0	16.7	6.0	15.0	4.0	13.3	15.0	100.0
	Vaccination	3.0	10.0	3.0	7.5	6.0	20.0	12.0	
	Treating the sick animals	1.0	3.3	5.0	12.5	4.0	13.3	10.0	100.0
	Spraying the animals	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	2.0	6.7	3.0	100.0
	Reporting outbreaks to veterinary authorities	0.0	0.0	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	100.0
Alternative traditional treatment	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	6.7	2.0	100.0	

Source: Field data, 2025

4.4 Treatment of Sick Cattle in 2023 and 2024

The findings of the present study indicated that (N=75/100) dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub-County sought treatment for sick animals from veterinary professionals, while the remaining (N=25/100) resorted to self-treatment. The preference for self-treatment was predominantly reported by small-scale farmers (n=10/30), while medium- and large-scale farmers engaged veterinary professionals. This finding is consistent with findings of Sahle et al. (2020) in Southern Ethiopia, where 73% of farmers consulted veterinary professionals and 27% treated animals themselves. Similarly, Perry and Grace (2009) highlighted in their sub-Saharan African livestock policy analysis that smallholder farmers frequently turn to self-treatment due to under-resourced veterinary systems and weak regulation of veterinary drug outlets. Furthermore, Lubinga et al. (2015) in Uganda's cattle corridor districts reported that approximately 68% of farmers sought veterinary assistance, while others relied on traditional remedies or over-the-counter antibiotics.

The (N=25/100) farmers who treated their own cattle reported several reasons and challenges that forced them to do so. Among the reasons given, limited access and scarcity of veterinary doctors (N=8/100) was the mostly cited challenge with the highest percentage being reported among the medium scale farmers (n=5/40). This finding is in agreement with the study conducted by Mwebesa et al. (2018) in western Uganda, which reported that medium scale farmers often complained of inadequate veterinary presence in their areas especially during disease outbreaks, forcing them to treat animals themselves. Other challenges reported included fear of losing animals due to lack of timely treatment and inaccessibility of farms, as shown in Table 4 below

Table 4: Showing who treated the sick animals as well as the reasons why farmers treated their own cattle

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Who treated the sick animals	Veterinary practitioners	20.0	66.7	31.0	77.5	24.0	80.0	75.0	100.0
	Farmers	10.0	33.3	9.0	22.5	6.0	20.0	25.0	100.0
Reasons why Farmers treat their cattle	Limited access and scarcity of veterinary doctors	2.0	6.7	5.0	12.5	1.0	3.3	8.0	100.0
	High cost of veterinary services	4.0	13.3	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	100.0
	Financial constraints and poverty	1.0	3.3	1.0	2.5	4.0	13.4	6.0	100.0
	Inadequate government and veterinary extension services	2.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	100.0
	Fear of losing animals due to lack of timely treatment	1.0	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
	Confidence and experience in self-treatment	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
	Remoteness and inaccessibility of farms	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.3	1.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

4.5 Quarantine measures for new cattle introduced on the farm

The findings of the present study as shown in Table 5 indicated that only (42.0%, N=100) dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub-County implemented quarantine measures when introducing

new cattle to their farms, while the majority (58.0%, N=100) did not. The practice of quarantining was more common among small-scale farmers (50.0%, n=30) and medium scale (40.0%, n=40), while large-scale farmers (36.7%, n=30) reported the least compliance. These findings are consistent with those of Ilbeigi et al. (2018), who conducted a cross-sectional survey of 110 dairy farms in Iran and found out that only 45% of farmers practiced any form of quarantine for new or returning animals.

Similarly, the study by Balinda et al. (2009) investigated FMD transmission dynamics during outbreaks in Uganda’s cattle corridor, including Kyankwanzi District and found out that failure to quarantine animals introduced from markets was a significant contributor to disease spread, despite the existence of Ministry of Agriculture guidelines recommending isolation. However, the current findings contradict with the findings by Sørensen et al. (2014) who conducted a study in Denmark where over 90% of farms enforced strict quarantine protocols when purchasing livestock. Their high compliance rates were linked to well-established regulatory frameworks, effective disease surveillance systems, and economic incentives for biosecurity practices.

On the other hand, the farmers (58.0%, N=100) who never implemented quarantine measures for the new cattle reported limited space and infrastructure (21.0%, N=100) as the major factor limiting the implementation of the practice more so among the medium scale farmers (25.0%, n=40). This finding is in agreement with the study by Cottrell et al. (2012), who noted that many farmers, especially those operating under land-constrained conditions, cited inadequate physical infrastructure as a major barrier to isolating newly introduced animals, thereby increasing disease vulnerability on farms.

Table 5: showing factors that fail farmers to follow quarantine measures for the new cattle

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Whether they follow quarantine measures for the new cattle	No	15.0	50.0	24.0	60.0	19.0	63.3	58.0	100.0
	Yes	15.0	50.0	16.0	40.0	11.0	36.7	42.0	100.0
What makes farmers fail to	Limited space and infrastructure	4.0	13.4	10.0	25.0	7.0	23.3	21.0	100.0

follow quarantine measures for the new introduced cattle	High costs of managing the new cattle separately	2.0	6.7	5.0	12.5	2.0	6.7	9.0	100.0
	Labor shortages and time constraints	1.0	3.3	3.0	7.5	5.0	16.7	9.0	100.0
	Limited resources (feeds, water)	6.0	20.0	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	8.0	100.0
	Trust in the sources of new cattle	1.0	3.3	2.0	5.0	3.0	10.0	6.0	100.0
	Lack of knowledge and guidance on quarantine procedures	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	1.0	3.3	2.0	100.0
	Need for immediate production and integration	1.0	3.3	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	2.0	100.0
	Easy monitoring of the new cattle with others	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.3	1.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

4.6 Vaccination against Foot and Mouth Disease FMD

The results (Table 6) show that most dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Subcounty (N=75/100) reported vaccinating their animals against Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD), with large-scale farmers making up the largest proportion (n=23/30). However, (N=25/100) of respondents indicated that they did not vaccinate, with small-scale farmers forming the majority within this group (n=8/30).

Regarding vaccination frequency, most farmers (N=59/100) reported only vaccinating during FMD outbreaks majorly among the large-scale farmers (n=22/30) and only (N=5/100) of farmers practiced biannual vaccination, primarily small-scale farmers (n=3/30).

The data implies that while a good number of farmers engage in vaccination against FMD, most do so inconsistently and only in response to outbreaks. This reactive rather than proactive approach undermines effective disease control and compromises herd immunity. It suggests a need for strengthened education and extension services focused on the importance of regular, preventive vaccination to mitigate the risks of FMD outbreaks, especially in areas prone to recurrent cases.

Similar patterns were observed by Shankar et al. (2019) in Maharashtra, India, where 68% of dairy farmers acknowledged vaccinating against FMD, but only 15% adhered to a regular

vaccination schedule. Most farmers reported vaccinating only during previous outbreak alerts issued by veterinary officers, mirroring the outbreak-driven behavior seen among farmers in Byerima. A study by Mesfine et al. (2020) in central Ethiopia revealed that 70% of farmers vaccinated their cattle only when there were reported cases in nearby farms. The researchers also found that inconsistent vaccine supply and limited awareness of FMD vaccination schedules were major contributing factors, aligning with the reactive and irregular vaccination behavior observed in Byerima Subcounty.

In contrast, Munyua et al. (2017) in Kenya found that over 80% of surveyed pastoralist households practiced biannual FMD vaccination, primarily due to strong community-based disease surveillance and active veterinary outreach programs. This regular preventive approach differs significantly from the findings in Byerima, where only 5% of farmers practiced biannual vaccination.

Table 6: showing how often farmers do vaccinate their cattle

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Whether they vaccinate their cattle	Yes	22.0	73.3	30.0	75.0	23.0	76.7	75.0	100.0
	No	8.0	26.7	10.0	25.0	7.0	23.3	25.0	100.0
How often do they vaccinate their cattle	Only during outbreaks	15.0	50.0	22.0	55.0	22.0	73.3	59.0	100.0
	Once a year	4.0	13.3	7.0	17.5	0.0	0.0	11.0	100.0
	Every 6 Months	3.0	10.0	1.0	2.5	1.0	3.3	5.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

4.7 Reasons for not vaccinating their cattle

Among the farmers who did not vaccinate their cattle (25.0%, N=100), the most frequently cited reason was the limited availability and supply of vaccines (10.0%, N=100) primarily reported by medium-scale farmers (12.5%, n=40) and high costs of vaccines and veterinary services (5.0%, N=100) especially among large-scale (3.3%, n=30). Other reasons included, concerns about vaccine safety and side effect and perception that vaccination is only necessary during disease outbreaks though with less frequency as shown in (Table 7).

The findings suggest that structural and economic barriers are key deterrents to FMD vaccination among farmers in Byerima Subcounty. The predominant issues of vaccine unavailability and cost highlight the need for government or donor-supported interventions aimed at improving vaccine supply chains and reducing financial burdens on farmers. Misconceptions about the necessity of vaccination outside outbreaks, along with safety concerns, reveal gaps in knowledge and awareness that could be bridged through farmer education campaigns and trust-building around veterinary services.

Comparable findings were reported by Ali et al. (2021) in rural Pakistan, where a large number of livestock farmers indicated that vaccine shortages and erratic government supply systems were the main reasons for poor FMD vaccination coverage. Farmers expressed frustration at long waiting periods for public vaccine campaigns, aligning with the supply limitations reported in Byerima. Similarly, Nkosi and Mokoena (2018) in South Africa found that the cost of vaccines and veterinary visits significantly discouraged smallholder and emerging commercial farmers from maintaining regular vaccination routines. This supports the cost-related concerns expressed by large-scale and small-scale farmers in the present study.

Table 7: showing reasons why farmers do not vaccinate their cattle

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Reasons for not vaccinating cattle	Limited availability and supply of vaccines	3.0	10.0	5.0	12.5	2.0	6.7	10.0	100.0
	High cost of vaccines and veterinary services	2.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	3.0	10.0	5.0	100.0
	Inaccessibility of veterinary professionals	2.0	6.7	2.0	5.0	1.0	3.3	5.0	100.0
	Concerns about vaccine safety and side effects	1.0	3.3	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	2.0	100.0
	Lack of veterinary infrastructure and support services	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
	Long distance to vaccine and veterinary services	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	100.0
	Perception that vaccination is only necessary during disease outbreaks	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.3	1.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

4.8 Cleaning and disinfection practices of barns and farm equipment

As shown in figure 4, the majority of dairy farmers (48.0%, N=100) reported that they sometimes cleaned and disinfected their barns and farm equipment, with the largest group being medium-scale farmers (57.5%, n=40). This was followed by farmers who rarely practiced disinfection (30.0%, N=100), predominantly large-scale farmers (43.3%, n=30). Only (10.0%, N=100) farmers reported always cleaning and disinfecting, most of whom were small-scale (16.7%, n=30). Conversely, (2.0%, N=100) farmers stated they often cleaned or disinfected at all, with small-scale farmers (3.3%, n=30) and large-scale farmers (3.3%, n=30) dominating this group.

The data implies that cleaning and disinfection practices among dairy farmers in Byerima Subcounty are inconsistent and suboptimal, with most farmers adopting irregular hygiene routines. The fact that a significant portion of farmers only disinfect "sometimes" or "rarely" indicates a potential risk for disease transmission within and between herds due to poor sanitation. The finding that some medium- and large-scale farmers never clean or disinfect is particularly concerning, as these farms typically house more animals and thus pose a higher risk for widespread outbreaks if hygiene is neglected.

Comparable concerns were observed in a study by Alhaji et al. (2016) in Nigeria, where only 20% of pastoral and agro-pastoral dairy herds practiced regular disinfection, and a majority acknowledged only occasional or seasonal cleaning of housing and equipment. Their findings align closely with the inconsistent cleaning practices noted in Byerima Subcounty. Similarly, Tebug et al. (2015) in Laos reported that while dairy farmers were aware of basic hygiene measures, few applied them consistently. The study highlighted that limited knowledge and absence of formal training contributed to irregular disinfection routines; a situation that reflects the hygiene behavior patterns among farmers in Byerima.

In contrast, Sridhar et al. (2020) in India found that over 70% of surveyed commercial dairy farms adhered to strict sanitation protocols, including daily cleaning and routine disinfection of milking areas and equipment. This high compliance rate was attributed to government-led hygiene campaigns and veterinary supervision, differing from the low adherence seen in Byerima Subcounty.

Figure 4: Showing how often farmers-maintained cleanliness and disinfection of farm tools and equipment

Source: Field data, 2025

4.9 Challenges to maintaining regular cleaning and disinfection practices

As shown in Table 9 the most commonly cited challenge to maintaining regular cleaning and disinfection of barns and equipment was labor shortage and limited workforce (N=23/100) with the highest percentage reported by large-scale farmers (n=8/30). This was followed by the hectic nature of regular maintenance (N=21/100), predominantly affecting large-scale farmers (n=9/30), indicating that larger farm sizes contribute to the difficulty and physical burden of maintaining consistent hygiene practices.

A smaller number of respondents mentioned challenges such as unfavorable weather conditions (N=4/100) mostly by medium-scale farmers (n=2/40) and fear of animal stress from disinfectants (N=3/100), mainly among medium-scale farmers (n=2/40), as shown in Table 10.

The data implies that physical labor constraints and the demanding workload associated with farm size significantly hinder consistent cleaning and disinfection among dairy cattle farmers. This suggests a need for labor support, improved cleaning systems, and farmer training to ensure better hygiene practices on dairy farms.

Garforth et al. (2013) in Nepal also noted that large-scale dairy farmers struggled to maintain regular hygiene due to the increased workload and larger herds, despite having more resources. The burden of routine tasks like cleaning and disinfecting was frequently delegated to undertrained laborers, contributing to inconsistent hygiene. In contrast, a study by Miller and Hall (2019) in Canada reported fewer difficulties in maintaining cleaning routines due to mechanized sanitation systems and structured labor roles on most dairy farms. These

technological advancements reduced reliance on manual labor and minimized disruptions caused by farm size or physical workload.

Table 8: showing challenges to maintaining regular cleaning and disinfection practices

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Challenges to regular sanitation and disinfection of barns and farm equipment	Labor shortage and limited workforce	6.0	20.0	9.0	22.5	8.0	26.7	23.0	100.0
	Hectic nature of regular maintenance	7.0	23.3	5.0	12.5	9.0	30.0	21.0	100.0
	High cost of high-quality cleaning and disinfection materials	7.0	23.3	9.0	22.5	1.0	3.3	17.0	100.0
	Limited access to cleaning materials and disinfectants	2.0	6.7	3.0	7.5	6.0	20.0	11.0	100.0
	Water scarcity and inadequate supply	4.0	13.3	3.0	7.5	0.0	0.0	7.0	100.0
	Financial constraints and low farm income	0.0	0.0	4.0	10.0	1.0	3.3	5.0	100.0
	Time constraints and competing priorities	1.0	3.3	2.0	5.0	2.0	6.7	5.0	100.0
	Large scale farm size	1.0	3.3	1.0	2.5	2.0	6.7	4.0	100.0
	Unfavorable weather conditions	1.0	3.3	2.0	5.0	1.0	3.3	4.0	100.0
	Fear of animal stress from disinfectants	1.0	3.3	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

4.10 Challenges to accessing veterinary services

Access to veterinary services for Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) was reported by a slight majority of farmers (54.0%, N=100), with small-scale farmers representing the highest proportion (60.0%, n=30). However, a substantial number of respondents (46%, N=100) reported limited access, with large-scale farmers leading (50%, n=30) followed by medium scale farmers (47.5%, n=40)

Among the farmers who never had access to veterinary services, the most common barrier to accessing these services was poor road networks and transport (13.0%, N=100) affecting all production scales, but especially large-scale farmers (13.3%, n=30) followed by high cost of veterinary services, primarily reported by large-scale farmers (20%, n=30). Other issues

included long distances to service providers, weak veterinary extension support, and favoritism or selective service delivery, with some large-scale farmers also citing poor communication and financial constraints as shown in table 10.

The data implies that while a good proportion of farmers can access FMD veterinary services, significant logistical and economic barriers still limit regular access, particularly for medium- and large-scale producers. These findings highlight the urgent need for better infrastructure, affordable veterinary care, and equitable service delivery to improve disease control and livestock productivity.

Ayele et al. (2016) in Ethiopia also found that while some farmers had access to veterinary services, systemic issues like long distances to service centers, inconsistent availability of veterinary staff, and service favoritism created inequitable access, particularly among mid-level producers. These obstacles mirror the structural and logistical barriers experienced in Byerima. In contrast, Reyes et al. (2021) in Chile documented more consistent access to veterinary care, thanks to a combination of strong road infrastructure, government-subsidized veterinary outreach, and coordinated farmer-vet networks. Such a structured support system significantly reduced service disparities between production scales, unlike the uneven access reported in Byerima.

Table 9: showing challenges to accessing veterinary services

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)		
Whether they have regular access to FMD veterinary services	Yes	18.0	60.0	21.0	52.5	15.0	50.0	54.0	100.0
Reasons For limited access to veterinary services	No	12.0	40.0	19.0	47.5	15.0	50.0	46.0	100.0
	Poor road networks and transport	4.0	13.3	5.0	12.5	4.0	13.3	13.0	100.0
	High cost of veterinary services	0.0	0.0	5.0	12.5	6.0	20.0	11.0	100.0
	Long distances to service providers	3.0	10.0	4.0	10.0	0.0	0.0	7.0	100.0
	Weak veterinary extension and government support	3.0	10.0	2.0	5.0	1.0	3.3	6.0	100.0

	Favoritism and selective service	2.0	6.7	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	100.0
	Farmer's financial constraints	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	2.0	6.7	3.0	100.0
	Poor communication	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	6.7	2.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

4.11 Challenges to compliance with FMD control practices

The findings of the present study revealed that limited access to vaccines was the most commonly reported challenge in implementing FMD control practices, cited by (N=34/100) dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub-County. This constraint was more pronounced among large-scale farmers (n=15/30) and small-scale (n=9/30) farmers. The higher proportion among large-scale farmers may be attributed to their larger herd sizes, which increase demand and amplify the impact of any supply shortages.

This finding is consistent with a study by Rufael et al. (2008) in Ethiopia, which reported that restricted vaccine availability especially during peak demand periods limited effective implementation of FMD control strategies. Farmers with larger herds reported greater difficulty in accessing sufficient doses, often due to inadequate distribution systems and delays in vaccine delivery. In contrast to the present study, studies conducted in high-income regions such as the Netherlands (van Roermund et al., 2010) found that vaccine access was rarely a limiting factor, largely due to structured national programs, subsidized vaccine provision, and coordinated outbreak response mechanisms. This contrast underscores the structural barriers faced in low-resource settings like Byerima subcounty of kyankwanzi district.

The study also found out that high costs of medication and vaccination (N=21/100) was also a significant barrier, especially among medium-scale farmers (n=11/40) and small-scale (n=7/30). This suggests that financial limitations affect the ability of small- and medium-scale farmers to access essential disease prevention and treatment services, possibly due to limited capital reserves and narrower operational margins. This finding is consistent with the finding from a study by Ali et al. (2017) in Pakistan which found out that economic constraints were among the leading reasons small and medium-scale farmers failed to vaccinate their animals against FMD. Their study revealed that many farmers were willing to vaccinate but cited unaffordable costs and lack of financial support from government bodies as key limitations to effective implementation of FMD control practices.

Furthermore, to support the findings of the current study, Alhaji et al. (2016) in Nigeria identified limited institutional support and high vaccination costs as significant obstacles to biosecurity and FMD control, particularly in pastoral and agropastoral communities. The study noted that while awareness was relatively high, actual implementation lagged due to lack of training, vaccine access, and funding. Other challenges mentioned included institutional shortcomings, labor shortages, and inadequate quarantine facilities as shown in Table 12 though these were reported with less frequency and did not exhibit a consistent pattern across the different production scales.

Table 10: showing challenges to compliance with foot and mouth disease control practices

Attributes	Responses	Scale of extensive dairy cattle production						Total (freq)	Total (%)
		Small scale(n=30)		Medium scale(n=40)		Large scale (n=30)			
		Frequen cy	Percent (%)	Frequenc y	Percent (%)	(Frequen cy	Percent (%)		
Challenges to compliance with FMD control practices	Limited access to vaccines	9.0	30.0	10.0	25.0	15.0	50.0	34.0	100.0
	High costs of medication and vaccination	7.0	23.3	11.0	27.5	3.0	10.0	21.0	100.0
	Limited access to veterinary services	5.0	16.7	4.0	10.0	3.0	10.0	12.0	100.0
	Disease spread through neighboring farms	2.0	6.7	4.0	10.0	2.0	6.7	8.0	100.0
	Financial constraints	3.0	10.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	6.7	7.0	100.0
	Lack of knowledge and awareness	1.0	3.3	2.0	5.0	3.0	10.0	6.0	100.0
	Inadequate quarantine facilities and biosecurity measures	1.0	3.3	2.0	5.0	1.0	3.3	4.0	100.0
	Government and institutional challenges	2.0	6.7	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	100.0
	Labor shortages to clean and disinfect farm tools	0.0	0.0	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	100.0
	Inadequate drugs for vaccination	0.0	0.0	1.0	2.5	1.0	3.3	2.0	100.0

Source: Field data, 2025

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5 Introduction

This chapter presents conclusions and recommendations by the researcher basing on the study findings and the research objectives.

5.1 Conclusions

The study assessed the compliance of dairy cattle farmers with Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices in Byerima Sub-County, Kyankwanzi District. Findings showed that overall knowledge and awareness of FMD was high across all scales of production but the actual compliance to the practices was sub optimal due to economic, institutional and logistical challenges.

Most of the respondents were familiar with the disease with the majority being the medium-scale farmers, followed by the small-scale farmers, and then the large-scale farmers. Awareness about the FMD control practices was high with the majority being the medium scale farmers followed by small scale farmers and lastly the large-scale farmers

Small-scale farmers, though familiar with the disease, relied heavily on informal information channels, which limited their understanding of technical practices such as vaccination schedules and biosecurity. Medium-scale farmers showed better knowledge, often gained through experience and periodic interaction with veterinary officers and large-scale farmers often gained knowledge and information through government extension services.

Key factors to compliance with FMD control practices varied across the different scales of production as follows. For small scale farmers, the most common factors were limited access to veterinary doctors, high costs of veterinary services and inadequate government extension services. Medium-scale farmers were mainly affected by limited availability and supply of vaccines and inaccessibility of veterinary professionals which discouraged routine engagement with preventive veterinary interventions. On the other hand, large-scale farmers were most affected by inadequate quarantine facilities and high costs veterinary services.

The challenges to compliance included the following according to the scale of production. For small-scale farmers limited access to vaccines and high medication and vaccination costs were the key reasons for non-compliance. For medium-scale farmers high medication and

vaccination cost and limited access to vaccines were the major constraints. For large-scale farmers limited access to sufficient vaccines and higher medication and vaccination together with limited access to veterinary services limited their compliance with the control practices of Foot and mouth disease. These findings confirm that although awareness is widespread, significant compliance gaps remain due to a mix of economic, knowledge-based, and service delivery constraints that vary across production scales.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, several recommendations are proposed to improve the management of foot and mouth disease among dairy cattle farmers in Uganda

5.2.1 Recommendations to Governments, Animal Health Organizations, and Veterinary Associations

Governments, animal health organizations, and veterinary associations should improve access to veterinary services by establishing well-equipped veterinary clinics close to farmers' farms or at least in every parish, to ensure timely and effective management of Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) outbreaks.

Governments and relevant authorities should provide adequate training and essential resources to veterinarians to enhance their capacity to deliver quality services, particularly in remote and underserved areas where veterinary care is often limited.

Veterinary extension services should be improved and expanded to ensure that farmers consistently receive accurate information, regular guidance, and practical support in preventing and managing FMD outbreaks.

Subsidy programs should be introduced to make FMD vaccines and treatments more affordable, encouraging broader adoption of control measures among farmers, especially those with limited financial resources.

Community sensitization campaigns should be intensified and widely implemented to educate farmers about the economic consequences of FMD, its modes of transmission, and the preventive actions necessary to control its spread.

5.2.2 Recommendations to Researchers, Extension Agents, and Agricultural Organizations

Researchers, extension agents, and agricultural organizations should actively monitor and evaluate Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) management practices through regular field surveys,

systematic collection of outbreak data, and assessments of farmer compliance with recommended prevention and control measures.

These stakeholders should work closely with veterinary departments to analyze disease trends and patterns, and to jointly design timely and effective intervention strategies based on real-time field evidence.

They should take the lead in developing and distributing practical, farmer-friendly educational materials and training modules that focus on FMD identification, proper reporting procedures, and appropriate responses to suspected or confirmed outbreaks.

Researchers, extension agents, and agricultural organizations should also support the creation of responsive feedback mechanisms that enable farmers to report challenges they face in disease control and to receive accurate, timely guidance from experts.

5.2.3 Recommendations to farmers

Farmers must actively participate in training programs organized by veterinary services and agricultural extension officers to equip themselves with vital knowledge on FMD prevention, early detection, and effective response strategies to reduce animal deaths caused by the disease.

They should immediately report any suspected FMD cases to local veterinary authorities instead of informing fellow farmers, and strictly adhere to vaccination programs and biosecurity measures recommended by experts.

Farmers must completely avoid practices that fuel the spread of the disease, such as uncontrolled animal movement and the use of contaminated tools.

Every farmer must uphold to consistent cleaning and disinfection of animal housing, strict isolation of sick animals, and active involvement in community sensitization forums in order to reduce the incidences of the disease spread.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah Azeem, I. R., Hassan, M. M., Muhammad Asad, G. K., Tehseen, A., & Aamir, S. (2020a). 10. A review on foot and mouth disease in dairy animals, etiology, pathogenesis and clinical findings. *Pure and Applied Biology (PAB)*, 9(1), Article 1.
- Abdullah Azeem, I. R., Hassan, M. M., Muhammad Asad, G. K., Tehseen, A., & Aamir, S. (2020b). 10. A review on foot and mouth disease in dairy animals, etiology, pathogenesis and clinical findings. *Pure and Applied Biology (PAB)*, 9(1), Article 1.
- Ahmed, Z., Velazquez-Salinas, L., Mwiine, F. N., Vander Waal, K., & Rieder, E. (2022). Complete Coding Genome Sequences of Five Foot-and-Mouth Disease Viruses Belonging to Serotype O, Isolated from Cattle in Uganda in 2015 to 2016. *Microbiology Resource Announcements*, 11(8), e00445-22. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mra.00445-22>.
- Ahmed, F., Singh, A., & Kaur, P. (2019). Analysis of Management and Health Practices in Dairy Farms of Punjab, India. *International Journal of Livestock Research*, 9(5), 37–45.
- Alhaji, N. B., & Odetokun, I. A. (2013). Assessment of biosecurity measures against highly pathogenic avian influenza risks in small-scale commercial farms and free-range poultry flocks in the north-central Nigeria. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 45(1), 157–165.
- Ali, A., Khan, I., & Shabbir, R. M. K. (2021). Constraints to livestock vaccination in rural Pakistan. *Journal of Veterinary Research*, 15(3), 198–206.
- Ali, S., Khan, M. A., & Rehman, T. (2017). Socioeconomic constraints in the adoption of FMD control measures among dairy farmers in Pakistan. *Journal of Animal and Plant Sciences*, 27(3), 730–738.
- Aslam, M., & Alkheraije, K. A. (2023a). The prevalence of foot-and-mouth disease in Asia. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1201578>

- Aslam, M., & Alkheraije, K. A. (2023b). The prevalence of foot-and-mouth disease in Asia. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science, 10*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1201578>.
- Ampaire, E. L., Kabunga, N., & Okoboi, G. (2020). Determinants of gender roles and benefits in livestock value chains: A case of dairy value chain in Uganda's central cattle corridor. *Journal of Agricultural Science, 12*(7), 42–52.
- Aslam, M., & Alkheraije, K. A. (2023). The prevalence of foot-and-mouth disease in Asia. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science, 10*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1201578>.
- Asiimwe, J. B., Muwanga, M., & Twinamasiko, M. (2020). Income sources and expenditure patterns of dairy farmers in Uganda: A study of the Central Cattle Corridor. *Uganda Journal of Agricultural Economics, 6*(2), 45–53.
- Ayelet, G., Gelaye, E., Negussie, H., & Asmare, K. (2012). Study on the epidemiology of foot and mouth disease in Ethiopia. *Revue Scientifique et Technique (International Office of Epizootics), 31*, 789–798. <https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.31.3.2153>
- Bahk, Y. Y., Cho, P. Y., Ahn, S. K., Lee, W.-J., Kim, T.-S., & Uganda. (2018). An Evaluation of Active Case Detection in Malaria Control Program in Kiyuni Parish of Kyankwanzi District, Uganda. *The Korean Journal of Parasitology, 56*(6), 625–632. <https://doi.org/10.3347/kjp.2018.56.6.625>
- Balamurugan, V., Kumar, R. M., & Suryanarayana, V. V. S. (n.d.). *past and present vaccine development strategies for the control of foot-and-mouth disease*.
- Baluka, S. A. (2016). Economic effects of foot and mouth disease outbreaks along the cattle marketing chain in Uganda. *Veterinary World, 9*(6), 544–553. <https://doi.org/10.14202/vetworld.2016.544-553>
- Barlett, C. P., Vowels, C. L., & Saucier, D. A. (2001). Meta-Analyses of the Effects of Media Images on Men's Body-image Concerns. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology, 27*(3), 279–310. <https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.2008.27.3.279>.

- Bebe, B. O., Udo, H. M. J., & Thorpe, W. (2003). Development of smallholder dairy systems in the Kenya highlands. *Outlook on Agriculture*, 32(2), 113–120.
- Benin, S., Thurlow, J., Diao, X., Kebede, G., & Schmidt, E. (2008). Agricultural growth and investment options for poverty reduction in Uganda. IFPRI Discussion Paper 00790. International Food Policy Research Institute.
- Blake, A., Sinclair, M. T., & Sugiyarto, G. (n.d.). *The Economy-Wide Effects of Foot and Mouth Disease in the UK Economy*.
- Brennan, M. L., & Christley, R. M. (2012). Biosecurity on cattle farms: A study in North West England. *BMC Veterinary Research*, 8(1), 71.
- Broughan, J. M., Maye, D., Carmody, P., Brunton, L. A., Ashton, A., Wapenaar, W., & Lahuerta-Marin, A. (2016). Farm-level biosecurity and health interventions: Farmers' experiences, knowledge and attitudes. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 128, 61–70.
- Cardwell, J. M., Lewis, E. G., Smith, R. F., et al. (2016). A longitudinal study of biosecurity practices on dairy farms in England, and their association with bovine tuberculosis. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 134, 14–22.
- Carrillo, C. (2012). Foot and Mouth Disease Virus Genome. In M. Garcia (Ed.), *Viral Genomes—Molecular Structure, Diversity, Gene Expression Mechanisms and Host-Virus Interactions*. InTech. <https://doi.org/10.5772/26930>
- Chandio, A., Rehman, A., Yuansheng, J., & Noonari, S. (2017). Importance of the Dairy Industry and Economic Growth in Pakistan: An Empirical Study. *Journal of Applied Environmental and Biological Sciences*, 7, 13–20.
- Chatikobo, P., Chikumba, N., & Ndlovu, L. R. (2014). Land tenure security and investment in livestock production in Zimbabwe. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 9(9), 857–864.

- Cheruiyot, M. K. (2017). *Factors Influencing Milk Production Project Among Small Scale Dairy Farmers in Bomet East Sub County, Bomet County, Kenya*. 03(09).
- Cottam, E. M. (2008). *Micro-evolution of foot-and-mouth disease virus* [PhD, University of Glasgow]. <https://eleanor.lib.gla.ac.uk/record=b2616102>.
- De Vries, J. (2008). Strategies for income diversification in smallholder livestock farming systems. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, 20(8), Article 121.
- Donaldson, A. I., Gloster, J., Harvey, L. D., & Deans, D. H. (1982). Use of prediction models to forecast and analyse airborne spread during the foot-and-mouth disease outbreaks in Brittany, Jersey and the Isle of Wight in 1981. *The Veterinary Record*, 110(3), 53–57. <https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.110.3.53>.
- Ekou, J., Lumu, R., & Akankwasa, D. (2023). Milk production and commercialization in Uganda: Opportunities and challenges. *Uganda Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 21(1), 49–57.
- FAO. (2021). *World dairy situation 2021*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO. (2022). *Milk production and trade in Africa*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Frössling, J., & Nöremark, M. (2016). The Swedish animal welfare and health surveillance system—current strengths and future challenges. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 127, 84–91.
- Fuller, F. H., Huang, J., Ma, H., & Rozelle, S. (2005). *The Rapid Rise of China's Dairy Sector: Factors Behind the Growth in Demand and Supply* (CARD Working Paper 05-WP 394). <https://doi.org/10.22004/ag.econ.18456>.

- Gakuya, F., Ombui, J., Maingi, N., Muchemi, G., & Ogara, W. (2011). Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices of Dairy Farmers on Foot and Mouth Disease in Kenya. *Journal of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Health*, 3(5), 161–168.
- Garcia, O., Hemme, T., Rojanasthien, S., & Younggad, J. (n.d.). *The Economics of Milk Production in Chiang Mai, Thailand, with Particular Emphasis on Small-Scale Producers*
- Gikunda, R. M., Kairu-Wanyoike, S. W., Bett, B. K., et al. (2020). Farmers' knowledge, attitudes and practices on foot-and-mouth disease in Kenya. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 182, 105062.
- Halima Abdallah. (2019). Impact of tick-borne diseases and acaricide resistance on Uganda's dairy sector. *Agricultural Development Review*, 34(2), 97–105.
- Hedge, N. G., Katole, S. C., & Kulkarni, D. N. (2005). Use of Indigenous Knowledge for Control of Foot and Mouth Disease in Cattle. *Indigenous Knowledge and Development Monitor*, 13(3), 27–30.
- Heffernan, C., et al. (2008). Biosecurity and UK farming: Farmers' perceptions, values and the role of trust in effective delivery. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 55(3–4), 263–270.
- Heng, N. T., Than, V. T., & Seng, H. (2019). Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices Regarding FMD among Farmers in Cambodia. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 51(7), 1921–1929.
- Hovi, M., et al. (2005). The role of farm animal health in public health: A review. *Veterinary Record*, 157(21), 649–652.
- Ilbeigi, K., Bokaie, S., Aghasharif, S., Soares Magalhães, R. J., & Rashtibaf, M. (2018). Risk factors for recurrence of FMD outbreaks in Iran: A case-control study in a highly

- endemic area. *BMC Veterinary Research*, 14(1), 253. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12917-018-1580-3>
- Jamal, S. M., & Belsham, G. J. (2013). Foot-and-mouth disease: Past, present and future. *Veterinary Research*, 44(1), 116. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9716-44-116>
- James, A. D., & Rushton, J. (2003). The economics of foot and mouth disease. *Revue Scientifique et Technique (International Office of Epizootics)*, 21, 637–644. <https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.21.3.1356>.
- Javira Ssebwami, N., Kalema, B., & Ssemujju, A. (2022). Uganda’s milk boom: Statistics, policies, and market dynamics. *East African Agribusiness Journal*, 5(2), 17–29.
- Josiah, J. M., Nyamache, A. K., Woldemariyam, F. T., Kariuki, C. K., Paeshuyse, J., & Kamau, J. M. (2024). Serotype Diversity of Foot And Mouth Disease Virus and Molecular Characterization of Serotype O Strains from 2019 and 2020 Outbreaks in Kenya. *Benha Veterinary Medical Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.21608/bvmj.2024.237871.1730>.
- Kafi, M., Mohammadi, G., & Razi, J. (2021). Socioeconomic determinants of foot-and-mouth disease awareness among dairy farmers in Iran. *Veterinary World*, 14(6), 1450–1457.
- Katongole, C., Nambi-Kasozi, J., & Nalule, A. S. (2017). Economic evaluation of large-scale dairy farming in Uganda. *East African Journal of Agricultural and Life Sciences*, 1(1), 27–35.
- Kalaiselvi, P., & Somasundaram, M. (2011). *World Wide Dairy Development—At a Glance*. <https://gnanaganga.inflibnet.ac.in:8443/jspui/handle/123456789/1422>
- Keeling, M. J., Woolhouse, M. E. J., May, R. M., Davies, G., & Grenfell, B. T. (2003). Modelling vaccination strategies against foot-and-mouth disease. *Nature*, 421(6919), 136–142. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01343>
- Kirunda, H., Kabi, F., Muwereza, N., Kabuuka, T., Magona, J. W., & Lukwago, G. (2012). Knowledge and perceptions of smallholder dairy farmers of cattle disease burdens in

- selected agro-ecological zones of Uganda. *Uganda Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 13(2), 107–116.
- Kisame, F. E., Wanyama, F., Basuta, G., Bwire, I., & Rwetsiba, A. (n.d.). *ground survey for medium - large mammals in kyankwanzi concession area*.
- Kitching, R. P., Hutber, A. M., & Thrusfield, M. V. (2005). A review of foot-and-mouth disease with special consideration for the clinical and epidemiological factors relevant to predictive modelling of the disease. *The Veterinary Journal*, 169(2), 197–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tvjl.2004.06.001>
- Knight-Jones, T. J. D., McLaws, M., & Rushton, J. (2017). Foot-and-Mouth Disease Impact on Smallholders—What Do We Know, What Don't We Know and How Can We Find Out More? *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 64(4), 1079–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.12507>
- Kostova-Vassilevska, T. (2004). *On The Use of Models To Assess Foot-And-Mouth Disease Transmission And Control* (No. UCRL-TR-205241). Lawrence Livermore National Lab. (LLNL), Livermore, CA (United States). <https://doi.org/10.2172/15014467>.
- Kristensen, E., & Jakobsen, E. B. (2011). Challenging the biosecurity concept in dairy herds: A review. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 98(3–4), 133–140.
- Kusasira, N. E. (2023). *Examination of the challenges facing the modernization of dairy farming practices in Uganda* [Masters, Dublin, National College of Ireland]. <https://norma.ncirl.ie/7007/>.
- Laanen, M., Persoons, D., Ribbens, S., et al. (2014). Relationship between biosecurity and production/antimicrobial treatment characteristics in pig herds. *Veterinary Journal*, 198(2), 508–512.
- Lapar, M. L. A., Tiongco, M., & Staal, S. (2003). Smallholder dairy policy in Vietnam. Research Report of the International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI)..

- Lazarus, D. D., Opperman, P. A., Sirdar, M. M., Wolf, T. E., van Wyk, I., Rikhotso, O. B., & Fosgate, G. T. (2021). Improving foot-and-mouth disease control through the evaluation of goat movement patterns within the FMD protection zone of South Africa. *Small Ruminant Research*, 201, 106448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2021.106448>
- Le, V. P., Nguyen, T., Lee, K.-N., Ko, Y.-J., Lee, H.-S., Nguyen, V. C., Mai, T. D., Do, T. H., Kim, S.-M., Cho, I.-S., & Park, J.-H. (2010). Molecular characterization of serotype A foot-and-mouth disease viruses circulating in Vietnam in 2009. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 144(1), 58–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2009.12.033>.
- Mavi, N. K., et al. (2006). Constraints in the Adoption of Improved Dairy Farming Practices by Dairy Farmers of Punjab. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 42(1), 50–55.
- Mangesho, P. E., Kurwijila, L. R., & Kimboka, E. J. (2017). Practices and challenges of dairy farmers in Tanzania: A case of selected villages in Njombe Region. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, 29(3), Article 49.
- Mazengia, H., Taye, M., Negussie, H., Alemu, S., & Tassew, A. (2010). Incidence of foot and mouth disease and its effect on milk yield in dairy cattle at Andassa dairy farm, Northwest Ethiopia. *Agriculture and Biology Journal of North America*, 1(5), 969–973. <https://doi.org/10.5251/abjna.2010.1.5.969.973>.
- Mugisha, A., Nampiima, D., & Nsubuga, G. (2014). Dairy farmers' perceptions of veterinary extension service delivery in central Uganda. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 46(8), 1501–1509.
- Munyua, P. M., et al. (2017). Strengthening surveillance and response to public health threats in Kenya. *BMC Public Health*, 17, Article 570.

- Muriuki, H. G., Wanyoike, F., & Bett, B. (2022). Understanding Knowledge Gaps in Foot and Mouth Disease Control among Smallholder Dairy Farmers in East Africa. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, 34(3).
- Munsey, A., Mwiine, F. N., Ochwo, S., Velazquez-Salinas, L., Ahmed, Z., Maree, F., Rodriguez, L. L., Rieder, E., Perez, A., & VanderWaal, K. (2019). Spatial distribution and risk factors for foot and mouth disease virus in Uganda: Opportunities for strategic surveillance. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 171, 104766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2019.104766>.
- Muroga, N., Kobayashi, S., Nishida, T., Hayama, Y., Kawano, T., Yamamoto, T., & Tsutsui, T. (2013). Risk factors for the transmission of foot-and-mouth disease during the 2010 outbreak in Japan: A case–control study. *BMC Veterinary Research*, 9(1), 150. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1746-6148-9-150>.
- Mwebesa, J. M., Otim, D. R., & Kansiime, D. (2015). Profitability of dairy farming enterprises in Uganda. *Uganda Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 16(2), 123–134.
- Nabikolo, D., Opondo, M., & Tumwesige, V. (2014). Rural livelihood strategies in Uganda: A study of smallholder mixed farmers in the Kigezi Highlands. *Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics*, 6(4), 163–170.
- Nabukenya, E., Matovu, D., & Maud, A. (2017). Gender Analysis of Livestock Value Chains: Evidence from Uganda. *International Journal of Gender and Women's Studies*, 5(1), 1–16.
- Nkosi, D., & Mokoena, M. (2018). Barriers to livestock vaccination among South African smallholder farmers. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 13(5), 197–205.
- Nourani, L., Safi, S., & Mohseni, S. M. (2021). Factors influencing farmers' communication channel selection in Afghanistan. *Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development*, 13(1), 1–7

- Nourani, L., Safi, S., & Mohseni, S. M. (2021). Factors influencing farmers' communication channel selection in Afghanistan. *Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development*, 13(1), 1–7.
- Odeng, C., Amany, S., & Tusiime, P. (2024). Drivers of Dairy Production Growth in Uganda: A Review of Trends and Policy Impacts. *African Journal of Livestock and Agricultural Research*, 11(1), 33–41.
- Okello, J., Okello, W., Muhanguzi, S., Kakuru, C., Nambo, E., Omodo, M., Ademun, R. A., Opiyo, F. L., Odoch, T., Kankya, C., Mwiine, F., & Nsawotebba, A. (2022). *Spatial and Temporal distribution of Foot and Mouth disease in cattle in Uganda from 2010 – 2021 (A retrospective study)*. In Review. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2013492/v1>.
- Pinto, J. (2017). Foot-and-Mouth Disease Situation Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Monthly Report.
- Pritchard, K., et al. (2015). Farmers' adoption of biosecurity practices: A review of the evidence. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 41, 123–132.
- Rachael, M., Kiprop, N. K., & Lutta, P. (2022). A global perspective on dairy production: Status, trends, and policy insights. *Global Journal of Dairy Science and Technology*, 8(3), 101–110.
- Radostitis, O. M., Gay, C. C., Blood, D. C., & Hinchcliff, K. W. (2000). *Veterinary Medicine: A textbook of the diseases of cattle, sheep, pigs, goats and horses (9th ed.)*. W.B. Saunders.
- Roy, P., et al. (2006). Constraints perceived by farmers in adoption of livestock practices. *Indian Journal of Animal Research*, 40(2), 90–94.
- Rufael, T., Catley, A., Bogale, A., Sahle, M., & Shiferaw, K. (2008). Foot and mouth disease in the Borana pastoral system, southern Ethiopia and implications for livelihoods and

- international trade. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 40(1), 29–38.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11250-007-9062-3>.
- Sambo, E., Musa, J., & Oyedemi, K. (2017). Education level of livestock farmers and adoption of improved management practices in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 21(2), 72–83.
- Saliu, B. A., et al. (2008). Adoption constraints of livestock vaccination programs in Nigeria. *African Journal of Livestock Extension*, 7, 36–42.
- Sarica, D., Demircan, V., Naziroglu, A., Aydin, O., & Koknaroglu, H. (2022). The cost and profitability analysis of different dairy farm sizes. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 54(5), 320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11250-022-03321-5>
- Sauer, J., & Latacz-Lohmann, U. (Eds.). (2013). *Efficient Innovation in Dairy Production—Empirical Findings for Germany*. <https://doi.org/10.22004/ag.econ.158865>.
- Singh, B., & Chander, M. (2005). Constraints faced by veterinarians in successful implementation of FMD vaccination programme in milch cattle and buffaloes. *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences*, 75(10), 1193–1195.
- Spear, R. (1982). The 1924 outbreak of foot-and-mouth disease in California: Lessons in disease control. *California Historical Quarterly*, 61(3), 247–264.
- Thomson, G. R., Vosloo, W., & Bastos, A. D. S. (n.d.). *The epidemiology and control of foot-and-mouth disease in sub-Saharan Africa*.
- Toma, L., Stott, A. W., Revoredo-Giha, C., & Kupiec-Teahan, B. (2015). A double-hurdle model of adoption and extent of adoption of green manure technology in the Midwest USA. *Agricultural Systems*, 130, 145–156.
- Tildesley, M. J., Bessell, P. R., Keeling, M. J., & Woolhouse, M. E. J. (2009). The role of pre-emptive culling in the control of foot-and-mouth disease. *Proceedings of the Royal*

- Society B: Biological Sciences*, 276(1671), 3239–3248.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2009.0427>.
- Turyahikayo, E., Twinamasiko, M., & Mwebesa, J. M. (2018). Crop-livestock integration among smallholder farmers in Western Uganda: An analysis of income and food security outcomes. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 13(14), 716–725.
- UBOS. (2021). Uganda Bureau of Statistics Annual Agricultural Survey Report 2021. Kampala: Government of Uganda.
- van Roermund, H. J. W., de Jong, M. C. M., & Stegeman, J. A. (2010). Surveillance and control of foot-and-mouth disease in the Netherlands: Scenario tree modeling to evaluate the probability of disease freedom. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 95(3–4), 154–165.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2010.04.003>.
- Velthuis, A. G. J., & Mourits, M. C. M. (2007). Effectiveness of movement-prevention regulations to reduce the spread of foot-and-mouth disease in The Netherlands. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 82(3), 262–281.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2007.05.023>
- Waiswa, D., & Günlü, A. (2023). Analysis of challenges facing and factors influencing the profitability of dairy cattle enterprises in southwestern Uganda. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*, 11(2), 207–214
- Wanyoike, F., Wambugu, S., & Kaitibie, S. (2015). Determinants of dairy production and marketing in East Africa: A case study of smallholder dairy farming in Kenya. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 47(2), 251–259.
- Wubshet, A. K., Werid, G. M., Teklue, T., Zhou, L., Bayasgalan, C., Tserendorj, A., Liu, J., Heath, L., Sun, Y., Ding, Y., Wang, W., Zaberezhny, A. D., Liu, Y., & Zhang, J. (2024). Foot and mouth disease vaccine efficacy in Africa: A systematic review and meta-

analysis. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 11.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2024.1360256>

Yaser, T., Bkear, N., Badr, Y., Ibrahim, E. E.-S., & Khodeir, M. H. (2023). Investigation of the effect of mutual vaccination with pest des petits ruminants and polyvalent foot and mouth disease vaccines on the immune response of sheep. *Open Veterinary Journal*, 13(12), 1669–1682. <https://doi.org/10.5455/OVJ.2023.v13.i12.16>

Yoo, H. S. (2011). Foot and Mouth Disease: Etiology, Epidemiology and Control Measures. *Infection & Chemotherapy*, 43(2), 178–185. <https://doi.org/10.3947/ic.2011.43.2.178>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX I

A questionnaire to be used for data collection on assessment of farmers’ compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease control practices among dairy cattle farms in Byerima Sub- County, Kyankwanzi District

INTRODUCTION

My name is Musasizi John, an undergraduate student doing Bachelor of Science in Agriculture and Livelihoods (BSAL) at Mbarara University of Science and Technology (MUST). Am undertaking a study on **“Assessment of farmers’ compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease control practices among dairy cattle farms in Byerima Sub- County, Kyankwanzi District”**. This study is done as a part of the requirement for the award of BSAL degree. You are kindly requested to participate in the study by answering the questions in the questionnaire. The information you give is confidential and will be used for academic purposes only. Thanks so much for taking your time to share your knowledge and experience!

Questionnaire no.....Date.....

District name.....

Sub-county name.....

Parish name

Village (cell).....

SECTION A: BACKGROUND CHARACTERISTICS

A1. Gender of the respondent

Male

Female

A2. How old are you?

21-30 years

31-40 years

41-50 years

51-60 years

Greater than 60 years

A3. What is your marital status?

Married

Single

Others (specify).....

A4. What is your highest level of education?

Primary

Secondary

Certificate

Diploma

Bachelors

A5. Are you the owner of this farm?

Yes

No

A6. If not, what is your role on this farm?

.....

A7. How long have you been engaged in dairy farming?

Less than one year

1-5 years

6-10 years

Over 10 years

Other (Specify).....

A8. Which livestock production system do you use to rear dairy cattle on your farm?

Intensive system Semi intensive system Extensive system

Others
(Specify).....

A9. Name the type and number of livestock you have on your farm? (*Please, complete the table below*)

Category	Type of livestock Species kept	Number of animals kept at the farm
Local (Indigenous)	Dairy Cattle	
	Beef cattle	
	Goats	
	Sheep	
	Pigs	
	Chicken	
	Others (Specify).....	
Crossbreeds	Dairy Cattle	
	Beef cattle	
	Goats	
	Sheep	
	Pigs	
	Chicken	
	Others (Specify).....	
Exotic breeds	Dairy Cattle	
	Beef cattle	
	Goats	
	Sheep	
	Pigs	
	Chicken	
	Others (Specify).....	

A10. Was dairy cattle production the major source of income in your family in 2023 and 2024?

Yes

No

A11. If No, what was the major source?

A12. What contribution did income from dairy cattle enterprise add to your overall income?

High contribution

Moderate contribution

Low contribution

Others (Specify).....

A13. What are your other sources of income at home?.....

A14. Give reasons for rearing dairy cattle

.....
.....
.....
.....

SECTION B: KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS OF FMD CONTROL PRACTICES AMONG DAIRY CATTLE FARMERS

B1. Are you familiar with Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD)?

Yes

No

B2. If yes, how did you first learn about FMD?

Government extension services

Veterinarian

Fellow farmers

Media (radio, TV, newspapers)

Others (specify).....

B3. Do you know the symptoms of Foot and Mouth Disease in cattle?

Yes

No

B4. If yes, which symptoms do you recognize as signs of Foot and Mouth Disease?

.....
.....
.....
.....

B5. If No, how do you know that your dairy cattle have acquired FMD?

.....
.....

B6. Are you aware of the FMD control practices recommended by veterinary authorities?

Yes

No

B7. If yes, which FMD control practices do you currently implement on your farm?

.....
.....
.....

B8. If No, why aren't you aware about these FMD control practices?

.....
.....
.....
.....

B9. How many heads of dairy cattle were treated for FMD and other diseases between 2023 and 2024? (*Fill the table below*);

Cause	Bulls	Steers	Adult cows	Heifers
-------	-------	--------	------------	---------

FMD				
2023				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
2024				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
Anaplasmosis				
2023				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
2024				
Trypanosomiasis treatment and control				
2023				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
2024				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
Helminthiasis				
2023				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
2024				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
Other diseases (Specify)...				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
Total cost				

B10. In your opinion, what were the major diseases which affected cattle in this Sub- County in 2023 and 2024?

B11. What were the most frequently used drugs to treat above diseases respectively?

.....

B12. Who treated sick cattle in 2023 and 2024?

Veterinary practitioners

Farmer

(Other Specify)

B13. If farmers, why did they treat their own cattle?

.....

B14. What was (is) the source of veterinary drugs used on the farm?

.....

B15. What is the distance moved by dairy cattle farmers to access a nearest veterinary drug shop?

.....

B16. How many heads of dairy cattle were vaccinated against the following diseases between 2023 and 2024? (*Fill the table below*);

Disease	Bulls	Steers	Adult cows	Heifers
Foot and Mouth Disease				
2023				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
2024				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
Anthrax				
2023				
Drug used				

Cost/head				
2024				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
Lumpy Skin disease				
2023				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
2024				
Drug used				
Cost/head				
Total cost				

B17. How many heads of dairy cattle died between 2023 and 2024? (*Fill the table below*)

Cause	Cause of deaths			
	Bulls	Steers	Adult cows	Heifers
Foot & Mouth Disease				
No. died 2023				
Average cost / value per category lost				
No. died 2024				
Average cost / value per category lost				
Anaplasmosis				
No. died 2023				
Average cost / value per category lost				
No. died 2024				
Average cost / value per category lost				
Other diseases caused death (specify)....				

Total cost / value of heads of cattle which were lost				
---	--	--	--	--

SECTION C: FMD CONTROL PRACTICES

C1. Do you follow quarantine measures for new cattle introduced into your farm?

Yes

No

C2. If no, what makes you fail to follow quarantine measures for new cattle introduced into your farm?

.....
.....
.....

C3. Do you vaccinate your cattle against foot and mouth disease (FMD)?

Yes

No

C4. If yes, how often do you vaccinate your cattle?

Every 6 months

Once a year

Only during outbreaks

Others (specify)

C5. If No, what are the reasons for not vaccinating your cattle?

.....
.....

.....
.....

C6. How regularly do you perform cleaning and disinfection of barns, equipment, and vehicles?

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

C7. What hinders you from maintaining regular cleaning and disinfection practices?

.....
.....
.....
.....

C8. Do you have regular access to veterinary services for FMD control?

Yes

No

C9. If No, what are the reasons for limited access to veterinary services?

.....
.....
.....
.....

SECTION D: CHALLENGES TO COMPLIANCE WITH FMD CONTROL PRACTICES

D1. What are the main challenges you face in complying with FMD control practices?

.....
.....
.....
.....

D2. According to you, how should the challenges above be solved to reduce on outbreak of FMD in this area?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

D3. In your own opinion, what measures can be undertaken to ensure that Dairy cattle keepers comply with the existing FMD control practices?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Thank you for your time and valuable insights!

THE END

APPENDIX II

A research consent form to be used to seek for consent from study participants

Study title

Assessment of farmers' compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease control practices among dairy cattle farms in Byerima sub-county, kyankwanzi district

Principal researcher

MUSASIZI JOHN

2021/BSAL/037/PS

Faculty of Interdisciplinary Studies (FIS)

Mbarara University of Science and Technology (MUST)

Study Supervisor

IVAN JJOOGA (PhD Scholar [Mak])

Department of Environment and Livelihood Support Systems (DELSS)

Faculty of Interdisciplinary Studies (FIS)

Mbarara University of Science and Technology (MUST)

P.O BOX 1410,

MBARARA

Introduction

You are being invited to participate in a study on the 'Assessment of Farmers' Compliance with Foot and Mouth Disease Control Practices on dairy cattle farms in Byerima Sub-County, Kyankwanzi District'. This form provides detailed information about the study, and it is important that you understand what participation entails before you agree to be part of the research.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess how dairy cattle farmers in Byerima Sub-County comply with Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control practices. The study aims to gather information that will help improve FMD management and control in the region.

Procedures involved

If you agree to participate in this study, the following will occur:

1. Interview/Survey: You will be asked to participate in an interview or survey about your farming practices, particularly related to FMD control measures. The questions will focus on the implementation of disease control measures on your farm.
2. Data Collection: The interview/survey will be conducted in a manner that is convenient for you, either in person or over the phone. The process will approximately take 30 minutes to complete.
3. Anonymized Codes: Your responses will be kept confidential. Your personal identity will not be attached to any responses. You will be assigned an anonymized code to ensure your privacy.

Voluntary participation

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You have the right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any time without facing any consequences or loss of benefits. If you decide to withdraw, all data collected up to that point will be removed from the study.

Confidentiality

All information you provide will be kept confidential. Your responses will be coded with an anonymized number or code to protect your identity. Only the research team will have access to the raw data, and any findings will be presented in aggregated form, ensuring that no individual can be identified.

Potential risks

There are no known risks associated with your participation in this study. However, if you feel uncomfortable at any point, you are free to withdraw from the study without any penalty.

Benefits

By participating in this study, you will be contributing to valuable research that aims to improve FMD control practices, benefiting both farmers and the wider community. However, there will be no direct financial or personal benefit to you from participating in the study.

Compensation

There will be no financial compensation for participating in this study. However, your participation will contribute to the improvement of farming practices in your region.

Contact information

If you have any questions or concerns about this study, or if you would like more information, please contact

Principal researcher
Musasizi john
0704550108 & 0780431011
Email: musaasizijohn2000@gmail.com

Or

Study supervisor
Ivan Jjooga (PhD Scholar [Mak])
0773802797
Email: jjoogaivan@must.ac.ug

Consent

By signing this form, you are agreeing to participate in this study. You acknowledge that you have read and understood the information provided, and that you are participating voluntarily. You also understand that you can withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Participant's Name.....

Signature of Participant.....

Date.....

Researcher's Name:

Signature of Researcher:

Date.....

APPENDIX III

Approval letter from the faculty of interdisciplinary studies of Mbarara university of science and technology.

MBARARA UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

P.O. Box 1410, Mbarara Uganda. Tel: +256 4856 60208; Fax: +256 4854 20782

Faculty of Interdisciplinary Studies (FIS)

Office of the Dean

Date: 17/12/2024

Ref: FIS/PF/.....

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

Re: Introductory Letter for MUSAISI JOHN Reg No. 2021/604103712

This letter serves to introduce the above named person who is a student at Mbarara University of science and technology. He/she is undertaking a BACHELORS DEGREE OF SCIENCE IN AGRICULTURE He/She is in his/her 3rd/4th year and as part of his/her study course, he/she is required to conduct a research on the Topic titled:

ASSESSMENT OF FARMERS COMPLIANCE WITH FOOT AND MOUTH DISEASE CONTROL PRACTICES AMONG DAIRY CATTLE FARMS IN BIERIMA SUB-COUNTY, KIANKWANI DISTRICT

Any assistance given to him/her to collect the data for his/her Research study is highly appreciated.

Yours faithfully

Betty Namusoke Okumu
Faculty Administrator

